

MAPPING THE SCHOLARSHIP OF THE REGULATION OF DARK PATTERNS

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF
CONCEPTS, REGULATORY
PARADIGMS, AND SOLUTIONS
FROM LAW AND HCI
PERSPECTIVES

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WEIWEI YI
ZHAO LI

CREATe

Mapping the Scholarship of the Regulation of Dark Patterns: A Systematic Review of Concepts, Regulatory Paradigms, and Solutions from Law and HCI perspectives*

Weiwei Yi and Zihao Li**

Abstract

In recent years, dark patterns, which are interface designs that manipulate user decisions, have raised growing regulatory concern. Yet scholarship on their governance remains fragmented, particularly in how the concept is defined, the harms are understood, and legal responses are framed. This paper offers a systematic review of 65 studies from Law and Human-Computer Interaction, following PRISMA guidelines. It identifies five root problems and layered harms, critiques sectoral regulations for their theoretical and enforcement limits, and synthesises proposed solutions, from doctrinal refinements and accountability measures to technical design interventions. Building on these findings, the paper argues that regulatory progress is hindered by the elusive nature of dark patterns, the difficulty of pinpointing actionable harms, and the expanding scope of the concept. It concludes by advocating a paradigmatic shift towards a proactive framework centred on 'diligent design', and outlines directions for collaborative, transdisciplinary research.

Keywords: Dark Patterns; Manipulative Design; HCI; Data Protection; Consumer Protection, Competition law

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** Weiwei Yi is PhD candidate and Zihao Li is Lecturer in Law and Technology, both at CREATE, University of Glasgow. For queries please contact Weiwei Yi at w.yi.1@research.gla.ac.uk.

1. Introduction

In the digital age, users engage daily with online services through interfaces and system designs,¹ yet often without awareness of the deliberate design choices embedded in these interactions.² This lack of scrutiny enables the deployment of *dark patterns* – interface manipulations that steer users toward unintended actions, such as unwanted purchases or data sharing³ – which cause various harms including harm to consumer welfare and privacy.⁴ While specific types (e.g., roach motel, bait-and-switch, trick questions)⁵ are now widely recognised, the phenomenon is increasingly situated within a broader backdrop of the socio-technological approach to technology in relation to modifications to users' choice architecture in and beyond the context of user interfaces.⁶

Although human-computer-interaction (HCI)⁷ researchers have led foundational work on dark patterns, including the development of taxonomies and detection methodologies, legal scholarship has only recently begun to address the regulatory implications. Compared to the depth of HCI studies, there is a lack of systematic analysis of how dark patterns are understood and addressed within legal and policy frameworks. Existing literature offers limited insight into

¹ Gaia Bernstein, 'A Window of Opportunity to Regulate Addictive Technologies' (2022) 2022 Wisconsin Law Review Forward 64.

² Daniel Susser, 'Invisible Influence: Artificial Intelligence and the Ethics of Adaptive Choice Architectures', *Proceedings of the 2019 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society* (ACM 2019) 404 <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3306618.3314286>> accessed 22 October 2023.

³ As with various definitions of 'dark patterns', this paper introduces the concept by referring to the preliminary definition provided by Harry Brignull, who first coined the term 'dark patterns'. See Harry Brignull, Mark Leiser, Cristiana Santos and Kosha Doshi, 'Deceptive Design' (2023) <https://www.deceptive.design> accessed 5 July 2024.

⁴ Arunesh Mathur, Mihir Kshirsagar and Jonathan Mayer, 'What Makes a Dark Pattern... Dark? Design Attributes, Normative Considerations, and Measurement Methods', *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Association for Computing Machinery 2021) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445610>> accessed 23 February 2023.

⁵ Colin M Gray, Cristiana Santos and Nataliia Bielova, 'Towards a Preliminary Ontology of Dark Patterns Knowledge', *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2023) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3544549.3585676>> accessed 9 June 2023.

⁶ Kerstin Bongard-Blanchy and others, 'I Am Definitely Manipulated, Even When I Am Aware of It. It's Ridiculous!' - Dark Patterns from the End-User Perspective', *Designing Interactive Systems Conference 2021* (ACM 2021) 763 <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3461778.3462086>> accessed 14 September 2023. See also Daniel Susser, Beate Roessler and Helen Nissenbaum, 'Technology, Autonomy, and Manipulation' (2019) 8 *Internet Policy Review* 7-8 <<https://policyreview.info/articles/analysis/technology-autonomy-and-manipulation>> accessed 4 October 2023.

⁷ 'Human-computer interaction is a discipline concerned with the design, evaluation and implementation of interactive computing systems for human use and with the study of major phenomena surrounding them.' See Thomas Hewett and others, 'ACM SIGCHI Curricula for Human-Computer Interaction' (Association for Computing Machinery 1992) 5 <<http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=2594128>> accessed 10 March 2025.

how legal scholars across jurisdictions conceptualise dark patterns, what legal regimes they interrogate, and what doctrinal or structural limitations may hinder regulation.

At a critical juncture where dark patterns are becoming central to digital harm regulation, a comprehensive review of the legal scholarship is urgently needed. Current discussions are fragmented across regimes (e.g., consumer, data protection, competition law), with little mapping of the underlying conceptual or normative approaches taken in legal discourse. Nor has sufficient attention been paid to what can be learned from existing academic contributions across jurisdictions to inform more coherent and future-proof regulatory strategies.

This research addresses these gaps through three key contributions. First, it systematically maps global legal scholarship on dark pattern regulation, identifying the field's core characteristics, including framings and aims, contexts, and jurisdictions. It demonstrates the unique characteristics of legal scholarship approaching dark patterns. It highlights five root problems and three layers of harm articulated in legal literature, and synthesises the problems of current regulations (i.e., in legal doctrines and governance approach), and outlines the primarily proposed regulatory solutions that are paradigmatic, supplemental, or technical.

Second, it critically evaluates, with a focus on the EU, the conceptual and institutional barriers that hinder comprehensive regulatory responses. It identifies ambiguities around the nature, harm, and scope of dark patterns and assesses proposed solutions. It then proposes a due diligence-based, design-embedded regulatory paradigm as a more proactive alternative to current harm-oriented approaches.

Last but not least, it bridges legal and HCI discourse to support interdisciplinary collaboration between law and HCI, by contextualising technical solutions under the dark pattern regulatory framework in a broader sense. Specifically, for policymakers, it clarifies promising and less productive regulatory paths. For legal researchers, it reveals underexplored areas (e.g., the discrepancy in the rationale of harms to competition and consumer welfare) and encourages synergy with HCI by supporting implementation and recognising technical solutions as legitimate regulatory instruments. For HCI researchers, it explains regulatory bottlenecks, clarifies the shifting conceptual boundaries of dark patterns in legal discourse, and suggests research directions that could facilitate a paradigm shift toward more proactive, design-based regulation.

2. Literature Review

Although there have been several reviews on dark patterns, current scholarship—predominantly driven by the HCI community—has not focused substantively on their regulation. Gray et al. developed a shared ontology by harmonising existing taxonomies across academic and regulatory domains, significantly advancing transdisciplinary understanding.⁸ However, their work does not aim to comprehensively review legal scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns. Gunawan et al. offer a detailed analysis of harms—including both material and non-material types—through a review of EU national case law, thereby evaluating the GDPR’s redress mechanisms.⁹ Santos et al. similarly examine regulatory documents and literature, identifying individual and collective harms and the treatment of harm in recent EU digital legislation.¹⁰ Yet, both studies centre harms rather than the broader regulatory landscape or paradigmatic challenges.

The absence of reviews from a normative legal perspective is also observed in broader conceptual studies. Mathur et al. identify definitions and taxonomies from various sources and connect them to normative theories but do not interrogate the legal frameworks governing dark patterns. Their work calls for HCI research to be more grounded in normative perspectives.¹¹ Chang et al. focus on deception theories and their application in design, regulatory, and research contexts, identifying a lack of theoretical engagement and calling for more structured, theory-driven inquiry into dark patterns.¹² Gray et al.’s systematic review of empirical HCI studies further acknowledges this gap, highlighting the lack of engagement with emerging legal discussions due to epistemological differences and methodological divergence.¹³

⁸ Colin M Gray and others, ‘An Ontology of Dark Patterns Knowledge: Foundations, Definitions, and a Pathway for Shared Knowledge-Building’, *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2024) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3613904.3642436>> accessed 12 February 2025.

⁹ Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara, ‘Redress for Dark Patterns Privacy Harms? A Case Study on Consent Interactions’, *Proceedings of the 2022 Symposium on Computer Science and Law (CSLAW ’22)*(2022) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3511265.355044>>.

¹⁰ Cristiana Santos, Viktorija Morozovaite and Silvia De Conca, ‘No Harm No Foul: How Harms Caused by Dark Patterns Are Conceptualised and Tackled under EU Data Protection, Consumer and Competition Laws’ [2025] *Information & Communications Technology Law* 1.

¹¹ Mathur, Kshirsagar and Mayer (n 4) 16.

¹² Weichen Joe Chang, Katie Seaborn and Andrew A Adams, ‘Theorizing Deception: A Scoping Review of Theory in Research on Dark Patterns and Deceptive Design’, *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Association for Computing Machinery 2024) 1 <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3613905.3650997>> accessed 16 February 2025.

¹³ Colin M Gray and others, ‘Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship: A Systematic Literature Review’, *Companion Publication of the 2023 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference* (Association for Computing Machinery 2023) 192 <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3563703.3596635>> accessed 29 October 2023.

On the policy side, several governmental and institutional reports address regulatory dimensions but are constrained by their specific mandates. The UK CMA's paper classifies online choice architecture (OCA)¹⁴ and discusses its implications within consumer and competition law frameworks but does not engage in broader regulatory critique.¹⁵ The US FTC report catalogues dark pattern types to raise public awareness and promote industry self-regulation, while only briefly touching on the legitimacy of practices.¹⁶ The OECD offers a comprehensive overview of existing laws and enforcement challenges but does not examine how legal scholarship systematises these frameworks or addresses doctrinal complexity.¹⁷ European Commission's behavioural reports incorporate dark patterns but are largely shaped by institutional perspectives, often limited to consumer protection, data protection, and competition law.¹⁸ Notably, the recent European Commission's Fitness Check Report assesses the adequacy of horizontal consumer law but discusses dark patterns only briefly, framing them narrowly within consumer law parameters.¹⁹

Despite the increasing regulatory attention to dark patterns as a source of digital harm, no systematic review to date has mapped the state of legal scholarship on this issue.²⁰ The regulatory discourse remains fragmented across domains and is often peripheral in interdisciplinary debates. This study addresses the gap by offering a structured and comprehensive review of legal scholarship on dark pattern regulation, illuminating its core framings, conceptual challenges, and proposed reforms. In doing so, it establishes a foundation for more integrated, theoretically-informed, and reform-oriented research in this emerging field.

¹⁴ According to this paper, OCA and dark patterns are posited as relevant and overlapping concepts, while OCA is larger. See pp.15-16.

¹⁵ Competition and Markets Authority, 'Online Choice Architecture - How Digital Design Can Harm Competition and Consumers (Discussion Paper)' (UK Competition and Markets Authority 2022) Discussion Paper CMA155 <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/online-choice-architecture-how-digital-design-can-harm-competition-and-consumers>>.

¹⁶ Federal Trade Commission, 'Bringing Dark Patterns to Light' (2022) Staff Report <<https://www.ftc.gov/reports/bringing-dark-patterns-light>> accessed 16 February 2025.

¹⁷ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 'Dark Commercial Patterns' (2022) 336 <<https://doi.org/10.1787/44f5e846-en>> accessed 25 July 2023.

¹⁸ Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers (European Commission) and others, 'Behavioural Study on Unfair Commercial Practices in the Digital Environment: Dark Patterns and Manipulative Personalisation Final Report' (Publications Office of the European Union 2022) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2838/859030>> accessed 6 February 2025.

¹⁹ European Commission, 'Commission Staff Working Document Fitness Check of EU Consumer Law on Digital Fairness (Digital Fitness Check)' (European Commission 2024) SWD(2024)230 final.

²⁰ We define the term 'regulation' broadly. See the Methodology chapter below.

3. Research Questions

To fill in the identified research gap, this paper systematically reviews the state-of-the-art scholarship regarding the regulation of dark patterns from the interdisciplinary perspectives of Law and HCI. This paper addresses an overall research question (RQ): What insights can be learned by reviewing HCI and legal scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns, and how can we shape more robust regulatory approaches? This question consists of five sub-questions. The first three questions (RQ1, RQ2, RQ3) are answered through thorough and structured qualitative research methods that reflect the findings of the systematic review, while the last two questions (RQ4, RQ5) serve as guiding threads for the discussion section and lead to a holistic discussion of promising regulatory approaches:

- RQ1: What are the basic characteristics of the scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns? (Section 5.1)
- RQ2: How does legal scholarship engage with and interpret the concept of 'dark patterns'? (Section 5.2)
- RQ3: What laws, doctrinal challenges, and pathways for reform are discussed to regulate dark patterns? (Section 5.3)
- RQ4: Why has a comprehensive regulatory framework remained elusive, despite growing demand for oversight? (Section 6.1)
- RQ5: How should we establish a robust regulatory framework? (Sections 6.2-6.4)

4. Methodology

To enable a more critical and constructive examination of the scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns, we adopted a broader interpretation of the term 'regulation'. This means that we not only cover the traditional narrow understanding of law and policy (by legislators, judges, government), but we also adopt the nascent concept of 'lex informatica' – the information policy rules formulated through technology – as coined by researcher Joel R. Reidenberg. Reidenberg acknowledges that law and government regulation are not the only sources of rulemaking, as technological capabilities and system design choices also impose rules on participants. However, policymakers are still at the centre of this type of policy instrument and should understand, encourage and elaborate on the rule-making in the form of network design, standards and system configuration that are *ex ante* self-enforced solutions, especially when

regulation, as a traditional (typically *ex post*) legal regime, falls short of regulating the fluid global digital activities.²¹

Therefore, our research includes both law and HCI for dark patterns' regulatory discussion rather than law papers alone. This is because, subjectively, the review aims to bridge the regulation of dark patterns knowledge that benefits both HCI and law sides and explore the potential for regulatory methods of technical characteristics (i.e., the case where regulation takes the form of infrastructural technical designs that rein in the dark patterns directly, aligning with the *lex informatica* idea above. See 4.2.1.); objectively, the HCI discipline remains the pioneer of dark pattern research and may pinpoint the regulatory limitations and directions in a grounded and practical manner, while the continuing collaboration within two disciplines blurs the differentiation and entails the consideration of papers based on content rather than origin.

To ensure that our review of the scholarship is methodologically systematic, transparent, reproducible and yields rigorous and credible findings, we follow the PRISMA approach²² to data collection and analysis (See Figure 1), which facilitates reliable knowledge benchmarking on the regulation of dark patterns between HCI and law disciplines.

4.1. Search Strategy

4.1.1. *Collecting and Screening Relevant Literature*

Considering that dark patterns are predominantly discussed in the research fields of information technology law and HCI, we used interdisciplinary databases that are particularly relevant to these two fields: JSTOR, HeinOnline, Scopus, Web of Science, and ACM Digital Library. To ensure an exhaustive review of the existing literature, no start date was specified for the publication date range. However, to collect relevant literature that meets adequate research quality standards, we used search engines to retrieve only peer-reviewed, English-language journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters through an advanced search with combined keywords: "dark pattern*" OR "manipulative pattern*" OR "deceptive pattern*" OR "ideceptive design*" OR "manipulative design*"²³. Wherever possible, the combined keywords

²¹ See Joel R Reidenberg, 'Lex Informatica: The Formulation of Information Policy Rules through Technology' (1997-1998) 76 Tex L Rev 553.

²² A systematic review is a review of a clearly defined question by employing systematic and explicit methods to identify, select, and critically evaluate pertinent research, and to collect and analyse data from the studies that are included in the review. See David Moher and others, 'Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement' (2009) 151 *Annals of Internal Medicine* 264. The preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis (PRISMA) is the guidance that supports rigorous systematic review, and it has been widely adopted across disciplines for various types of research, including dark pattern research. See eg Gray and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship' (n 13).

²³ These selected keywords are commonly used substitutes for 'dark patterns' by scholars.

were searched in "title, abstract, and indexing/keywords" (Web of Science and Scopus); where not available, "full text" was searched (ACM Digital Library, JSTOR, HeinOnline) to capture titles and abstracts for later review. To further target the regulatory discussion of dark patterns, we specified the research fields of 'Law' and 'HCI' whenever possible. On 14th November 2023, we downloaded 678 articles from the selected databases. After removing duplicates, we retained 586 papers for the data screening process. (Figure 1)

4.2. Exclusion and inclusion criteria

4.2.1. First-round screening: inclusion criteria

In this step, we started the first-round screening manually with the following inclusion criteria, based on the article's title, abstract, and indexing keywords. (For articles that we deem potentially relevant but with limited details, we tag them as *Maybe*, and the two researchers jointly decide after a process of full-text reading and discussion in the second-round screening).²⁴

- 1) The article should explicitly use the term "dark pattern(s)" or substitutes (i.e., deceptive/manipulative design(s)/pattern(s)).
- 2) The article should explicitly contain regulatory discussions regarding dark patterns (including legal and regulatory theories).²⁵

After the first screening, we excluded 476 articles (tagged *out*) that did not meet the inclusion criteria, leaving 110 papers (tagged *in* and *maybe*) for a second, full-text screening. Additionally, during this phase, we excluded non-papers, call for papers, workshops, papers not written in English, and those that were not accessible (e.g., papers with outdated links, institutional access limits).

4.2.2. Second-Round Screening: Inclusion Criteria and Division of Paper Types

To further screen the most relevant corpus, we read through the full text of each paper. We look for substantial discussions on dark pattern regulation (at least there is one section discussing dark patterns), and then divided the eligible literature into Group 1: law papers (including

²⁴ Different strategies are adopted for various databases to focus on papers containing regulatory discussions. For papers from HeinOnline, which are more law-oriented and often feature substantial regulatory discussions, we examine how keywords appear in these papers. For papers from the ACM Library that are more relevant to computer and information science, we particularly assess whether the words in the abstracts signal potential regulatory discussion and verify this through full-text reading. For the other three interdisciplinary databases where 'search by disciplines' is available, we lock on HCI/CS and Law/Social Science and similarly look for relevant keywords in abstracts.

²⁵ We refer to regulatory discussion as a primary discussion of law, of theories related to law, of regulation theories, and discussions of technology as a form of law to pursue policy goals.

empirical and theoretical) and Group 2: HCI papers (empirical and theoretical). Papers are classified as either type according to the primary research topic they examine or evaluate. When the distinction is not immediately apparent for some papers, as legal issues are discussed throughout the text, we decided to include them as law papers. This arrangement benefits the research in gaining more material to answer RQ2, which further helps enrich findings and deepen discussion (See Table 1).²⁶

After the previous step, for the rest of the HCI papers that do not show outstanding concerns of law topics, we deploy a second set of inclusion criteria for HCI papers to comply with our research focus on at least regulatory discussions of dark patterns:

- 1) The audience that the article explicitly addresses must include policymakers or legal researchers. (i.e., we do not infer such intention from the content. Therefore, papers only focusing on 'design ethics' or 'better designs' or that only address HCI designers/communities would not fall within the scope).
- 2) The article substantially engages with legal or regulatory discussions (i.e., articles that merely include a sentence of 'call for more legal attention to the focused topic,' or simply promote detection methods with a claim that 'this approach can inspire legal discussions/is helpful for policymakers,' or only mention legal aspects as descriptive backgrounds without substantial discussion of regulation will not be included).²⁷

After the second screening, 65 papers were retained, with 50 law papers (40 theoretical papers, 10 empirical papers) and 15 HCI papers (3 theoretical HCI papers, 12 empirical HCI papers).

²⁶ For instance, we define the following as law papers: Jamie Luguri and Lior Jacob Strahilevitz, 'Shining a Light on Dark Patterns' (2021) 13 *Journal of Legal Analysis* 43. and Colin M Gray and others, 'Dark Patterns and the Legal Requirements of Consent Banners: An Interaction Criticism Perspective', *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2021) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3411764.3445779>> accessed 9 December 2023. The following references define empirical research and empirical law papers: Malcolm Williams, *The SAGE Dictionary of Social Research Methods* (SAGE Publications, Ltd 2006) 91-92 <<https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857020116>> accessed 23 May 2024.; Peter Cane and Herbert M Kritzer (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Empirical Legal Research* (Oxford University Press 2010) 2 <<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199542475.001.0001>> accessed 23 May 2024.

²⁷ Although we acknowledge that there is an abundance of HCI papers that could inform and inspire regulators and legal researchers in various ways and contribute to the discussion on the regulation of dark patterns, considering the purpose of our research (i.e., mapping the regulation of dark patterns) and our limited resources for data management and analysis, it would be less rigorous to assume the authors' intent to discuss regulatory paradigms through their findings, or compatibility to situate the findings for a regulatory context, without the authors properly justifying or providing more information on that. Moreover, even though we reference the theory of *Lex Informatica*, it is necessary for HCI papers to be vocal and explicit with a similar illustration leading to a discussion of the current legal framework, in order to pass the screening.

Figure 1: the PRISMA Diagram.

4.3. Data Analysis

Given the diverse research questions (RQs) with different research objectives, we use both content and thematic analysis to address them.²⁸ Content analysis is suited to questions that require categorisation and quantification of textual data, such as the presence, frequency, or distribution of certain references. For example, whether a paper explicitly frames dark patterns as a regulatory problem, or which jurisdictions are mentioned, can be coded into categories and counted. Each code is meticulously described and stored in a codebook for review, and this method allows comparisons across the corpus by means of frequency tables and other structured outputs. This makes content analysis an appropriate choice for questions where concrete, directly identifiable answers are sought.

Accordingly, we use content analysis to code directly identifiable and quantifiable answers to all sub-questions in RQ1 (framings and aims, contexts, jurisdictions), the first two sub-questions in RQ2 (roles of dark pattern discussions in the corpus; references to definitions and approaches

²⁸ The content analysis and thematic analysis used in this research are informed by the following references: Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke, 'Can I Use TA? Should I Use TA? Should I Not Use TA? Comparing Reflexive Thematic Analysis and Other Pattern-Based Qualitative Analytic Approaches' (2021) 21 *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research* 37; Lisa Webley, *Qualitative Approaches to Empirical Legal Research* (Oxford University Press 2010) <<https://academic.oup.com/edited-volume/35077/chapter/299091384>> accessed 23 May 2024.

to taxonomies), and the first sub-question in RQ3 (laws regarding dark patterns discussed). We adopt the codes of the 'framing' section from Gray et al.'s codebook for HCI papers and answered the first sub-question in RQ1 deductively.²⁹ We chose this codebook because it is comprehensive and of high quality, deriving from a meticulous systematic review of empirical studies on dark patterns. The codes are naturally reusable for the same 'framings' question (for HCI papers) in our research, which is retained intact to compare with the 'aims' question (for law papers) and hence to yield constructive insights. In contrast, for the rest of the codes to answer other research questions, we conducted a pilot study to generate the codebook inductively. Codes for RQ3 are non-exclusively distributed,³⁰ while other questions are exclusively coded based on relevance. (See Appendix: The codebook for content analysis)

Thematic analysis, by contrast, is used where the answers are less directly observable and require interpretation of meaning. For instance, when asking what root problems and harms of dark patterns are identified, or what doctrinal challenges and solutions are proposed, the material cannot simply be tallied. Instead, recurring ideas must be grouped into broader themes that capture underlying reasoning. We use open and axial coding to develop these themes systematically and to interpret the patterns that emerge in relation to the research questions.³¹ (See Appendix: The list of codes/themes for thematic analysis)

To leverage the collective expertise that is needed for this research, the research team consists of one researcher with both social science and legal backgrounds who is dedicated to the regulation of dark patterns and experienced in qualitative research, and one researcher with both computer science and legal backgrounds who is dedicated to technology regulation and has expertise in comparative law. For the pilot coding, the first researcher selected 35 papers (i.e., 54% of the corpus of 65) at random to generate codes for the initial codebook of content analysis, ensuring that the sample reflected diversity across jurisdictions and disciplines. This codebook is then reviewed by both researchers and where disputes on codes were raised, the first researcher traced back to the data and refined the codes accordingly.

²⁹ The 'Framing' section of Gray et al.'s codebook is employed with the same definition here. This section of the codebook is updated by the addition of a new code (i.e., non-empirical/theoretical), in order to reflect HCI papers that are non-empirical and are not included by the initial codes. This adjustment was made to render the codebook more suitable for the research at hand. See the original codebook in Gray and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship' (n 13) 191.

³⁰ This means that more than one code can be distributed to a paper to answer the same question.

³¹ Axial coding is a method used to establish connections between categories and subcategories within qualitative data. It forms linkages that unveil emergent themes and facilitate the creation of new categories or subcategories. This process enables researchers to make theoretical claims about the patterns and relationships found in their data. See Nathaniel Simmons, 'Axial Coding' in Mike Allen (ed), *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Communication Research Methods*, vol 4 (SAGE Publications 2017) 80-82

After reaching a consensus on the codebook for content analysis, the first author coded the full corpus of 65 papers according to the predefined codes, in tandem with an open coding process in preparation for thematic analysis. After the first round of coding, the first researcher reviewed the codes from the open coding process and grouped themes based on the similarities among codes under the research question. To validate consistency, the second researcher independently coded 15 randomly selected papers (i.e., 23% of the corpus) according to the codebook. All discrepancies between the two coders were discussed until consensus was reached, and the codebook was refined where necessary. During this process, the team invited three external experts in empirical research in law and HCI to review and give suggestions for the codes and themes. Eventually, both researchers refined the codes and themes accordingly, checked the consistency of the codes across the dataset, and reached a full consensus on all code applications after multiple rounds of discussion and resolution of conflicts.

Research questions	Sub-research questions <i>(Footnotes to necessary definitions attached)</i>	Operationalisation of the coding process <i>(See the corresponding codebook for more detailed coding rationale for specific codes as well as footnotes of corresponding findings for more explanation of results).</i>	Analysis type	Data type
Objectives for RQ1: Grasping the basic characteristics of the scholarship, identifying emerging areas for further research, and complementing previous research.				
RQ1: What are the basic characteristics of the scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns? (Section 5.1)	What are the 'Framings' of the studies? (Section 5.1.1) [Footnote 32]	Gray et al.'s codebook was designed for empirical studies. We add a 'non-empirical/theoretical' code to capture HCI papers beyond their original scope without distorting their value. We code data with reference to Gray et al.'s approach (e.g., literature analysis sections, contribution framings) while ensuring exclusive categorisation.	Content analysis	HCI [15]
	What are the 'Aims' of the studies? (Section 5.1.1) [Footnote 32]	To ensure consistency, codes are applied exclusively to each paper. Primary aims are identified by analysing the introduction, conclusion, and relevant parts of the text. Where multiple aims exist, we consider the length and depth of discussion, prioritising those directly involving dark patterns.	Content analysis	Law [50]
	What are the 'Contexts' of the literature? (Section 5.1.2) [Footnote 36]	Codes are applied exclusively, based on the major topical context in which dark patterns are discussed. Following Gray et al., we use 'Digital Service' as a catch-all when other codes are not suitable.	Content analysis	All [65]
	What are the 'Jurisdictions' involved in the studies? (Section 5.1.3)	If a paper focuses on a specific region, country, or law/policy document, we code that jurisdiction. Where none is specified or multiple regions are considered, we code multi-jurisdictions.	Content analysis	All [65]

Objectives for RQ2: Delineating the contemporary understandings of dark patterns by legal researchers and how they approach the discussion of dark patterns in legal studies. Assisting researchers from different disciplines in identifying a shared foundation of knowledge for future collaboration				
RQ2: How does legal scholarship engage with and interpret the concept of dark patterns? (Section 5.2)	What roles do the dark pattern discussions play in the law literature? (Section 5.2.1)	We examine the length, placement, and structure of the dark pattern discussion, along with wording that indicates its purpose.	Content analysis	Law [50]
	How does the law literature refer to definitions and approach taxonomies of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.2)	We record works cited in full explanations of dark patterns. Where multiple citations appear, we note them all and rank the most frequently adopted studies. We also identify approaches to taxonomies based on explicit references to HCI terminology and the extent to which authors emphasise the role of taxonomies.	Content analysis	
	What are the root problems of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.3) [Footnote 58]	We identify root problems of dark patterns by examining article structure and the logic of arguments on how upstream factors or phenomena lead to effects, including dark patterns.	Thematic analysis	
	What are the identified harms of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.4)	We identify harms of dark patterns by examining article structure and the logic of arguments on the consequences or effects derived from them.	Thematic analysis	
Objectives for RQ3: Providing a comprehensive mapping of the regulatory landscape, deepening the analysis by examining doctrinal challenges underlying laws, systematically compiling them, and highlighting promising routes for regulatory enhancement.				
RQ3: What laws, doctrinal challenges, and pathways for reform are discussed to regulate dark patterns? (Section 5.3)	What laws regarding dark patterns are discussed? (Section 5.3) [Footnote 99]	We cluster laws according to their shared major functions (see footnote 99 for the explanation of this theory, and 100-101 for examples).	Content analysis	All [65]
	What are the doctrinal challenges of the corresponding laws? (Section 5.3.1) [Footnote 102]	Using the categories in Section 5.3, we examine recurring doctrinal issues in different laws and group them into themes based on problem similarity.	Thematic analysis	
	What revisions of regulation are proposed to solve dark patterns? (Section 5.3.2)	We group suggested regulatory revisions by their scale, magnitude, and form.	Thematic analysis	

Discussion		
RQ4: Why has a comprehensive regulatory framework remained elusive, despite growing demand for oversight? (Section 6.1)	Discussing inherent factors that hinder the establishment of a comprehensive regulation, based on our findings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The normative 'nature' problem • The 'harms' problem • The 'scope' problem
RQ5: How should we establish a robust regulatory framework? (Section 6.2-6.4)	Discussing promising routes for future regulation and collaborative research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promising technical and regulatory solutions • Diligent designs as a new paradigm: beyond proving harm and embracing a proactive, design-embedded regulatory framework • Future research opportunities

Table 1: Explanations for Research Questions

5. Findings

5.1. The basic characteristics of the scholarship (framings and aims, contexts, jurisdictions)

To map scholarship on dark pattern regulation, we first examine framings (HCI papers) and aims (law papers)(Section 5.1.1), alongside contexts (Section 5.1.2) and jurisdictions (Section 5.1.3).

5.1.1. Framings and aims³²

For the 50 law papers, most aim to *assess the existing law* (38%), while *evaluations of the legitimacy* of a practice are the least framed (14%). Comparatively, among the 15 HCI papers, the majority are likely to be *taxonomy-building* (33.34%). For instance, synthesising a collective multi-layer taxonomy of dark patterns using regulatory and academic literature,³³ or identifying new types of dark patterns in multi-modal scenarios or live-stream e-commerce.³⁴ Papers with *descriptive* or *detection-focused* framings are fewer (each at 13.3%), while only 6.6% are

³² Framings are defined as 'different methodological goals and limitations that reflect the primary intent of the research contribution', in line with the original definition in Gray et al.'s codebook. Aims are defined as the primary objectives and contributions of the research as observed.

³³ Gray, Santos and Bielova (n 5).

³⁴ Johanna Gunawan and others, 'A Comparative Study of Dark Patterns across Web and Mobile Modalities' (2021) 5 Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3479521>>; Qunfang Wu and others, 'Malicious Selling Strategies in Livestream E-Commerce: A Case Study of Alibaba's Taobao and ByteDance's TikTok' (2023) 30 ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3577199>> accessed 18 August 2023.

experimental/causal, and none are *evaluative*. Additionally, we identify *theoretical* papers (20%) that do not contain empirical elements.³⁵

These findings align with Gray et al.'s review of HCI scholarship in reflecting diverse framings, though with greater emphasis on taxonomy-building and an absence of evaluative work. We also note difficulties in classifying some papers as purely 'HCI' or 'law', highlighting the interdisciplinary nature of dark pattern research, which combines normative assessment of 'darkness' with empirical identification of design 'patterns'. This blurring of boundaries has fostered deeper cross-disciplinary collaboration and encouraged empirical studies in legal scholarship.

Figure 2: Framings and Aims.

5.1.2. Contexts³⁶

Regarding the contexts, the majority investigate dark patterns holistically and at a macro level (*Digital Services*) and tend to merely exemplify the diversity of dark patterns (38.5%).³⁷ Nonetheless, many articles still focus on micro-interactions with *user interfaces on websites or apps* (e.g., cookie banners/consent management interfaces, checkout processes on shopping

³⁵ For example, Arvind Narayanan and others, 'Dark Patterns: Past, Present, and Future: The Evolution of Tricky User Interfaces' (2020) 18 *Queue* 10:67. Mathur, Kshirsagar and Mayer (n 4); D Susser and V Grimaldi, 'Measuring Automated Influence: Between Empirical Evidence and Ethical Values' (2021) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3461702.346253>>.

³⁶ Contexts are defined as the major thematic domains within which dark patterns are discussed.

³⁷ See eg Kirsten Martin, 'Manipulation, Privacy, and Choice' (2021) 23 *North Carolina Journal of Law & Technology* 452; Lindsay Wilson, 'Is There a Light at The End of the Dark-Pattern Tunnel?' (2023) 91 *George Washington Law Review* 1048.

websites, content reporting interfaces on apps) (30.8%).³⁸ Meanwhile, papers that emphasise the roles and *effects of platforms* or related subjects in dark pattern practices tend to be legal or theoretical (16.9%).³⁹ *Algorithms and artificial intelligence* (9.2%) and *games and gaming* (4.6%) remain the least discussed, but still stand out as emerging themes where regulatory discussion is seeing growth.⁴⁰ The varied focuses of papers, ranging from macro-level discussions on general impacts to micro-level analyses of user interactions within specific scenarios, reflect the multifaceted nature of dark pattern research across disciplines.

Figure 3: Contexts.

5.1.3. Jurisdictions

Regarding jurisdictions, apart from studies that show a *multi-jurisdictional* focus (32.3%), most studies focus on the *United States* (33.8%), while the *European Union* (either at the EU level or national level) represents the third most studied region (27.7%). A minority of studies cover *the United Kingdom* (3.1%), *Canada* (1.5%), and *China* (1.5%). Clearly, although many papers do not

³⁸ See eg Hana Habib and others, “‘Okay, Whatever’: An Evaluation of Cookie Consent Interfaces”, *Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI ’22)* (Association for Computing Machinery 2022) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3501985>>; Arunesh Mathur and others, ‘Dark Patterns at Scale: Findings from a Crawl of 11K Shopping Websites’ (2019) 3 *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3359183>>; Ben Wagner and others, ‘Regulating Transparency? Facebook, Twitter and the German Network Enforcement Act’, *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (Association for Computing Machinery 2020) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372856>> accessed 18 April 2024.

³⁹ See eg Mark MacCarthy, ‘Enhanced Privacy Duties for Dominant Technology Companies’ (2021) 47 *Rutgers Computer and Technology Law Journal* 1.

⁴⁰ Tegan Cohen, ‘Regulating Manipulative Artificial Intelligence’ (2023) 20 *Scripted*; Sheldon A. Evans, ‘Pandora’s Loot Box’ (2022) 90 *The George Washington Law Review* 376.

specify jurisdictions, the United States and the European Union dominate the regulatory discussion on 'dark patterns' and related terms, influenced by the language of publication.

Figure 4: Jurisdictions.

This overview of the scholarship highlights emerging research areas, the different teleological orientations of HCI and law, and jurisdictions where further research is needed. It complements Gray et al.'s findings: we apply similar codes to capture the characteristics of dark pattern regulation scholarship while providing counterpart codes for legal literature, which are largely argument-oriented. Together, these supplements Gray et al.'s systematic review of empirical dark pattern research and enable interdisciplinary comparison between HCI framings and legal aims, offering a more comprehensive view of current scholarship.

5.2. The engagement with and interpretation of the concept of 'dark patterns' in legal scholarship

This section exclusively focuses on the law literature and elucidates whether and to what extent legal researchers have participated in the debate on dark patterns and thus provided an opportunity for knowledge alignment between legal and HCI researchers that could illuminate future research directions on the regulation of dark patterns. It first scopes the roles of dark pattern discussions (Section 5.2.1), legal researchers' understandings of dark patterns by looking at the definitions they refer to, and the manners in which they approach dark pattern taxonomies (Section 5.2.2). It further clusters the root problems (Section 5.2.3) and the harms (Section 5.2.4) identified in the legal scholarship.

5.2.1. The roles of dark pattern discussions in law literature

Among the 50 legal papers reviewed, those treating dark patterns *as the main focus* account for the largest share (38%). Many papers position dark patterns *as a case or theme* discussed independently or alongside other major subjects (e.g., as one aspect of the usability of cookie consent interfaces,⁴¹ or compared with behavioural advertising, personalisation, and recommendation systems)⁴² (30%). Other papers use dark patterns *as examples* (24%) as part of broader subjects (e.g., ‘platform nudges’,⁴³ the concept of online manipulation⁴⁴), which the papers primarily address. Some papers set dark patterns *as the context* and backdrop to introduce the main topics (8%).⁴⁵

Figure 5: Types of engagements with ‘Dark patterns’.

⁴¹ Kristina Lapin and Laima Volungevičiūtė, ‘Improving the Usability of Requests for Consent to Use Cookies’ in Cezary Biele and others (eds), *Digital Interaction and Machine Intelligence*, vol 710 (Springer Nature Switzerland 2023) <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-37649-8_19> accessed 9 December 2023.

⁴² Sébastien Fassiaux, ‘Preserving Consumer Autonomy through European Union Regulation of Artificial Intelligence: A Long-Term Approach’ [2023] *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 1.

⁴³ Abbey Stemler, Joshua E Perry and Todd Haugh, ‘The Code of the Platform’ (2019) 54 *Georgia Law Review* 605.

⁴⁴ Shaun B Spencer, ‘The Problem of Online Manipulation’ (2020) 2020 *University of Illinois Law Review* 959.

⁴⁵ See eg Sheldon A. Evans (n 43).

5.2.2. Definitions referred to and approaches to taxonomies of dark patterns in law literature

5.2.2.1. References of definitions, approaches to dark pattern types and taxonomies

Legal scholarship on dark patterns predominantly relies on definitions from HCI scholarship rather than legal and policy documents. Brignull's definition is the most frequently referenced,⁴⁶ followed by Mathur et al.,⁴⁷ then Gray et al.,⁴⁸ and lastly, Luguri and Strahilevitz.⁴⁹ However, unlike the focus on taxonomies typical in HCI literature on dark patterns,⁵⁰ half of the papers (50%) *neither engage with taxonomies* nor use specific HCI jargon or subcategories. Some (36%) only reference dark pattern types as examples, particularly when examining the effects of platforms, while only a few (14%) make taxonomy discussions their objectives, proposing, refining,⁵¹ or evaluating taxonomies.⁵² This suggests that legal scholarship tends to examine dark patterns holistically and may insufficiently discuss the diverse natures of different dark pattern types.

⁴⁶ Papers commonly refer to two sources. The first one is Harry Brignull, 'Dark Patterns: Dirty Tricks Designers Use to Make People Do Stuff' (*90 Percent of Everything*, 8 July 2010) <<https://www.90percentofeverything.com/2010/07/08/dark-patterns-dirty-tricks-designers-use-to-make-people-do-stuff/>> accessed 25 March 2025.. The other one is from 'Deceptive Patterns' <<https://www.deceptive.design/>> accessed 8 March 2024.

⁴⁷ Most references are made to the 2019 study (Mathur and others (n 41).) rather than the 2021 review in 2021 (Arunesh Mathur, Mihir Kshirsagar and Jonathan Mayer, 'What Makes a Dark Pattern... Dark? Design Attributes, Normative Considerations, and Measurement Methods', *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Association for Computing Machinery 2021) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445610>>.)

⁴⁸ Colin M Gray and others, 'The Dark (Patterns) Side of UX Design', *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2018) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3173574.3174108>> accessed 19 January 2024.

⁴⁹ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29).

⁵⁰ Gray and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship' (n 13) 190–191.

⁵¹ See eg Silvia De Conca, 'The Present Looks Nothing like the Jetsons: Deceptive Design in Virtual Assistants and the Protection of the Rights of Users' (2023) 51 *Computer Law and Security Review* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2023.105866>>.

⁵² See eg Alison Hung, 'Keeping Consumers in the Dark: Addressing "Nagging" Concerns and Injury' (2021) 121 *Columbia Law Review* 2483.

Figure 6: Types and taxonomies of dark patterns.

5.2.2.2. *The divergent scopes of dark patterns by some legal scholars*

We also noted discussions among legal researchers about expanding the concept of dark patterns to systemic issues, including personalised forms.⁵³ Examples include design patterns in non-traditional interfaces such as voice and gesture-based systems and virtual reality. These discussions explore how customisation and user profiling could enhance the influence of dark patterns by targeting specific vulnerabilities of individuals or groups.⁵⁴ Additionally, elements like loot boxes in video games are identified as dark patterns that could be intensified through gamer profiling.⁵⁵ The intertwining of dark patterns with AI is noteworthy, with some researchers discussing 'second-generation dark patterns' employed by AI to create 'hypernudges,' or referring to the 'unacceptable risk systems' under the proposed EU AI Act as 'dark pattern systems'.⁵⁶ This broader understanding of dark patterns aligns with HCI researchers' views on advanced personalised UIs as the future of dark patterns, moving beyond the basic forms currently prevalent and exploited by companies.⁵⁷ The implications of this development in legal scholarship will be discussed in Section 6.1.

⁵³ The impact of the evolving diversity of dark pattern scope will further be evaluated in the discussion section.

⁵⁴ Mason Marks, 'Biosupremacy: Big Data, Antitrust, and Monopolistic Power over Human Behavior' (2021) 55 UC Davis Law Review 513, 535; Silvia De Conca (n 54).

⁵⁵ Sheldon A. Evans (n 43) 428.

⁵⁶ Stefano Faraoni, 'Persuasive Technology and Computational Manipulation: Hypernudging out of Mental Self-Determination' (2023) 6 Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence 4; Vera Lúcia Raposo, 'Ex Machina: Preliminary Critical Assessment of the European Draft Act on Artificial Intelligence' (2022) 30 International Journal of Law and Information Technology 88.

⁵⁷ Narayanan and others (n 38) 79; Susser and Grimaldi (n 38).

5.2.3. *The root problems of dark patterns in law literature*

Through thematic analysis of the legal sources, we identify five root problems⁵⁸ (themes) that derive from or catalyse dark patterns: the invisibility of digital design, platform effects and digital market competition, human bias and vulnerability, (attention-seeking) business models and conflicts of interest, and power imbalance over information and design.

The invisibility of digital design

A dominant theme in the corpus is that the online environment is an indispensable contextual component of dark pattern practices. For example, it is pointed out that the uniqueness of dark patterns lies in the infinite and instant malleability of software interfaces, as design choices can be tweaked and updated through low-cost online experiments and automation tools. The vast potential gains from the direct result of expanding digitisation and globalisation fuel the prevalence and influence of dark patterns.⁵⁹ Beyond A/B testing, papers say that technologies such as behavioural analytics, user profiling and targeting, and even artificial intelligence have gradually given dark patterns more power over users.⁶⁰ As information technology "sits almost entirely outside conscious awareness," users seldom ponder the inner workings, but still actively use it daily; dark patterns benefit from the same invisibility.⁶¹ Even though the screens are tangible, designs that incentivise overuse and impulsivity remain invisible.⁶² Such invisibility of dark patterns has profound implications for long-term thinking,⁶³ which may "increase the risk that society will not engage in interpretive flexibility" and enable the technology to rapidly reach the phase of closure, at which point few social reflections on the choices of design and use would occur.⁶⁴

Platform effects and digital market competition

Many sources examine dark patterns through the roles and effects of platforms in the digital market, often viewing them as an abuse of platform(market) power.⁶⁵ Compared with brick-and-

⁵⁸ Root problems are defined as the upstream or underlying factors that lead to the emergence and prevalence of dark patterns.

⁵⁹ Justin Hurwitz, 'Designing a Pattern, Darkly' (2020) 22 North Carolina Journal of Law & Technology 57, 69; Lirio Barros and others, 'The Rise of Dark Patterns: Does Competition Law Make It Any Brighter?' (2022) 21 Competition Law Journal 136, 140; Alison Hung (n 55) 4.

⁶⁰ Jon M Garon, 'Protecting Public Health Amidst Data Theft, Sludge, and Dark Patterns: Overcoming the Constitutional Barriers to Health Information Regulations' (2023) 56 Akron Law Review 206; Sheldon A. Evans (n 43) 428; Silvia De Conca (n 54) 18; Faraoni (n 59) 4.

⁶¹ Daniel Susser, Beate Roessler and Helen Nissenbaum, 'Online Manipulation: Hidden Influences in a Digital World' (2019) 4 Georgetown Law Technology Review 1, 33-34.

⁶² Bernstein (n 1) 73.

⁶³ Fassiaux (n 45) 8.

⁶⁴ Bernstein (n 1) 73.

⁶⁵ Olivier Sylvain, 'A New Telecommunications Act: Prioritizing Consumer Protection and Equality Telecommunications Act of 1996 Symposium' (2022) 37 Berkeley Technology Law Journal 281, 305; Gregory Day and Abbey Stemler, 'Are Dark Patterns Anticompetitive?' (2020) 72 Alabama Law Review 1, 24.

mortar counterparts, digital platforms face fewer reputational concerns and competitive pressures since users commonly encounter inferior exit options, greater lock-in due to their investment in these platforms, and little regulation of harmful practices towards consumers.⁶⁶

However, regarding how the structure of market competition influences dark pattern practices, scholars' opinions diverge. Some argue that the increasing centralisation of market power by a handful of platforms and the lack of competition invalidate the market's self-correction process, leading to a deficiency of viable alternatives for consumers. In this context, firms can design interfaces to addict, subtly influence, or manipulate users and 'force purchasers to do something they would not do in a competitive market'.⁶⁷ However, other academics argue that it is the ever-fiercer competition in the digital market that pushes companies to engage in exploitative designs intentionally, arguing that in the presence of consumer cognitive bias and increased competition, companies could be passively forced to 'phish for phools' (e.g., using dark patterns to exploit consumers), 'because if they do not, they will be replaced by competitors that will'.⁶⁸

Human bias and vulnerability

Human bias and vulnerability are captured by most scholars as one of the essential reasons why dark patterns are effective. For instance, bounded rationality, which links to more normative concepts like 'human bias' and 'vulnerabilities', is commonly recognised in the corpus as a fundamental concept for understanding the effectiveness of dark patterns. The theories sometimes referred to by legal researchers are the dual-system theory by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky, or the nudge theory (including discussions of 'choice architecture', 'liberal paternalism', and 'nudge and sludge') by Thaler and Sunstein.⁶⁹ Legal scholars typically explain how dark patterns are designed to make use of various heuristics in conditions of imperfect information, to exploit individuals' limited time, attention, and brainpower, to push them to adopt rules of thumb for efficiency and quick solutions, and to 'program them for specific behaviour' at the cost of their long-term best interest.⁷⁰

(Attention-seeking) business models and conflicts of interest

Sources recognise that tech companies' attention-seeking business models motivate dark patterns. Platforms often offer low-cost or free services to attract attention, designing interfaces that nudge or hook users, creating addiction through dopamine rushes. For example,

⁶⁶ Caleb N. Griffin, 'Systemically Important Platforms' (2022) 107 Cornell Law Review 445, 475.

⁶⁷ Peter O'Loughlin, 'Cognitive Foreclosure: Rethinking Antitrust' (2021) 38 Georgia State University Law Review 1097, 1167; See also MacCarthy (n 42) 71-72; Alison Hung (n 55).

⁶⁸ Lauren E. Willis, 'Deception by Design' (2020) 34 Harvard Journal of Law & Technology 115, 151; Lirio Barros and others (n 62) 141; Caleb N. Griffin (n 69) 475.

⁶⁹ See eg Day and Stemler (n 68); Stemler, Perry and Haugh (n 46); Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29).

⁷⁰ Lirio Barros and others (n 62) 138-139; Lapin and Volungevičiūtė (n 44) 193-194; Hurwitz (n 62) 62.

Day and Stemler claim that companies would implement the 'attention cycle' rationale (i.e., the causal loop of 'attention', 'surveillance and experimentation', 'addiction') into interface design, by hooking users with free services (e.g., Instagram's photo filtering system, Uber gamification design for drivers), which enables the capture of user data that facilitates A/B testing and identifies and implement designs that 'best stimulate the release of neurochemicals essential to addiction'. This increases user engagement on the platform, facilitating greater personal data collection and ad sales (and continues the attention cycle loop).⁷¹

Meanwhile, some scholars believe that the conflict of interest between users and service providers is the primary driver of dark patterns.⁷² Digital platforms do not hold the best interests of users in mind and show indifference, if not outright exploitation, towards users' privacy and other interests.⁷³ When the 'growth hacking mantra' is adopted for a business to pursue solely the maximisation of certain metrics such as growth and engagement, dark patterns become inevitable and even welcomed by designers, as success is measured solely by business metrics related to ads, website, or app performance.⁷⁴ Even without this aggressive mantra, the business model creates a core dilemma of balancing revenue needs and legal compliance. For example, a consent wall may constitute a privacy dark pattern by preventing freely given consent, yet free access without barriers may jeopardise revenue.⁷⁵ This close-knit relationship between the freemium (low-price) business model and the derivative conflicts of interest undermines the classic corporate model between consumers and service/product providers, which is based on attracting consumers with desirable products at competitive prices.⁷⁶

Derivative problems: Power asymmetry over information and design

Another theme that emerges from the corpus is that the imbalance of power over information underpins the potency of dark patterns. Consumer data collected by platforms is the main source of the growing knowledge about individuals and groups that exacerbates the information imbalance and transforms into the power of manipulation. People may remain unaware that they have been subjects of A/B testing and online experiments, and that this information is used to

⁷¹ Day and Stemler (n 68) 7-8; Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara (n 9) 181; Bernstein (n 1) 69-70.

⁷² Ryan Calo, 'Digital Market Manipulation' (2013) 82 *George Washington Law Review* 995, 1044; Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64) 35; Bernstein (n 1) 74.

⁷³ Woodrow Hartzog and Neil Richards, 'The Surprising Virtues of Data Loyalty' (2022) 71 *Emory Law Journal* 985, 36-37.

⁷⁴ Lauren E. Willis, 'Deception by Design' (2020) 34 *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology* 115, 150.

⁷⁵ Gray and others, 'Dark Patterns and the Legal Requirements of Consent Banners' (n 29) 11.

⁷⁶ Caleb N. Griffin (n 69) 30.

create and refine dark patterns.⁷⁷ Ultimately, dark patterns utilising this information asymmetry enable vendors to have more or better information than users, creating other power imbalances that exploit consumers, such as in commercial transactions.⁷⁸

Similarly, some scholars propose that the asymmetry of design power is another factor. Even though it is increasingly recognised that 'Design is everything...[D]esign is power',⁷⁹ platforms typically hold the design power as choice architects, configuring how choices are presented and thus imposing a significant impact on user decision-making.⁸⁰ Platforms are given 'too much power', regarding the implementation, and this power imbalance results in practices ranging from nudging users to overlook cookie policies to implanting more complex dark patterns.⁸¹ Such design power imbalance is continuously exacerbated as power continues to be concentrated in a handful of technology companies, leading to weakened user participation and negotiation over feasible design alternatives.⁸²

In sum, these observed factors (themes) collectively explain the emergence and prevalence of dark patterns in the digital environment. Contrary to minor opinions that see dark patterns as merely an online replication of offline unfair practices,⁸³ our findings stress the unprecedented feature of dark patterns supported by the digital environment and technologies, influenced by the unique landscape of digital market competition and the inherent dilemma of business models. Moreover, the power imbalance of information and design may have changed 'the face of market manipulation to the point that it strains consumer protection law',⁸⁴ which further leads to calls for regulatory paradigm changes to focus on dealing with the power imbalance (See Section 6.3).⁸⁵

⁷⁷ Jamie Luguri and Lior Jacob Strahilevitz, 'Shining a Light on Dark Patterns' 13 43, 45; Gray and others, 'Dark Patterns and the Legal Requirements of Consent Banners' (n 29) 12; Thomas D Haley, 'Illusory Privacy' (2022) 98 *Indiana Law Journal* 75, 95.

⁷⁸ Mark Leiser and Wen-Ting Yang, 'Illuminating Manipulative Design: From "Dark Patterns" to Information Asymmetry and the Repression of Free Choice Under Information Asymmetry and the Repression of Free Choice Under the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive' 34 *Loyola Consumer Law Review* 484, 506.

⁷⁹ Alison Hung (n 55) 2486.

⁸⁰ Stemler, Perry and Haugh (n 46) 625.

⁸¹ Gerhard Seuchter and others, 'The Crux of Cookies Consent: A Legal and Technical Analysis of Shortcomings of Cookie Policies in the Age of the GDPR' [2020] *Jusletter IT* 9.

⁸² Konrad Kollnig and others, "'We Are Adults and Deserve Control of Our Phones": Examining the Risks and Opportunities of a Right to Repair for Mobile Apps', *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability* (Association for Computing Machinery 2023) 22 <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3593013.3593973>>.

⁸³ Gregory M Dickinson, 'Privately Policing Dark Patterns' 57 *Georgia Law Review* 1633, 1648.

⁸⁴ Calo (n 75) 1049.

⁸⁵ Hartzog and Richards (n 76) 988.

5.2.4. *The harms of dark patterns in law literature*

In this section, we synthesise the harms of dark patterns identified within the legal corpus into themes of harm to individuals, the market and competition, as well as society.

5.2.4.1. *Harms to individuals*

We notice that the most pronounced harms of dark patterns are to individuals. For example, the harm to individual decision-making ability caused by imposing labour or cognitive burdens is extensively recognised in the corpus, typically taking the form of constant distractions, excessive times required to complete tasks, and emotional distress, among others.⁸⁶ Comparatively, we discover that monetary harm is less emphasised in legal scholarship than in HCI scholarship. The long-term harm of addiction is also reflected in the sources, and it is claimed that companies have implemented dark design patterns (e.g., gamification, reinforcement reward design) that cause users to become addicted to the product, leading to various mental health issues, and the literature particularly stresses the amplification of damage to vulnerable groups such as children.⁸⁷ Additionally, we find that the recognition of harms shows regional disparity: addiction as a harm of dark patterns tends to be recognised in the US, while such harm is not widely recognised in the EU at the point of our data collection.

We notice a common narrative in the corpus, which is the tendency to associate dark patterns with harms to human rights and common values, such as autonomy, privacy, and fairness. In line with Gunawan et al.'s findings, almost all papers discuss, to some extent, the harm to individual autonomy or self-determination by impairing individuals' decision-making capacity.⁸⁸ We also notice from the sources that the harm to privacy ranges from well-known cases of consent interface designs to the emerging cases of private sphere surveillance.⁸⁹ Similarly, harms to fairness between traders and consumers are also commonly discussed, alongside evaluations of consumer protection frameworks.⁹⁰

⁸⁶ Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara (n 9) 183; Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64) 64; Faraoni (n 59) 5; Day and Stemler (n 68) 17.

⁸⁷ Caleb N. Griffin (n 69); Kollnig and others (n 85); O'Loughlin (n 70); Mark Warner, 'The Need for Legal Rules on Dark Pattern Website Activities' (2019) 3 International Journal for the Data Protection Officer and Privacy Counsel 7; Leon Y Xiao, 'Shopping Around for Loot Box Presence Warning Labels: Unsatisfactory Compliance on Epic, Nintendo, Sony, and Microsoft Platforms' (2023) 1 Games: Research and Practice 1; Bernstein (n 1).

⁸⁸ Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara (n 9) 183.

⁸⁹ Silvia De Conca (n 54).

⁹⁰ See eg Lauren E. Willis (n 71); Leiser, M.R. and Caruana, M., 'Dark Patterns: Light to Be Found in Europe's Consumer Protection Regime' (2021) 10 Journal Of European Consumer And Market Law 237; Johanna Gunawan and others (n 37); Dickinson (n 86).

5.2.4.2. *Harms to the market and competition*

We notice that the discussion of harms from market and competition perspectives has grown since Mathur et al.'s review.⁹¹ Some researchers argue that the harm to market competition stems from dark patterns interfering with market participants' (consumers') decision-making processes in transactions, which subsequently results in reduced market efficiency that accumulates into anti-competitive effects and harms to consumer welfare and market trust, especially when dark patterns are deployed by players with market power.⁹² However, we also observe a discrepancy in scholars' beliefs on dark patterns' effect on competition and downstream consumer welfare, which will be further discussed in Section 6.1.2.

5.2.4.3. *Harms to society*

We identify that dark patterns' harm to society primarily originates from their disruption to the effective functioning of laws. For instance, scholars believe that in the context of privacy and data protection, dark patterns compromise the consent mechanism, which is central to contemporary privacy and data protection regimes.⁹³ One point worth highlighting is that we have discovered that dark patterns can also subvert regulatory objectives beyond the commonly acknowledged protection of consumer welfare or privacy. For example, it is pointed out that dark design patterns used by Facebook in the platform's reporting procedures for hate speech and terrorist content have imposed a series of redirections and obstructions on reporters, undermining the implementation of Germany's Network Enforcement Act,⁹⁴ which may jeopardise democracy and national security. From a broader perspective, it is proposed in a source that 'dark patterns distract from two of the central objectives of the European Union's digital single market: creating the right conditions and a level playing field for digital networks and innovative services to flourish and maximise the growth potential of the digital economy'.⁹⁵ Additionally, some researchers believe that dark patterns undermine individuals' capacity for self-government and their ability to pursue their own goals, further harming democracy at a

⁹¹ Mathur, Kshirsagar and Mayer (n 4) 11. This numerical discrepancy may result from our inclusion of competition law papers that treat dark patterns as a theme or as examples within a broader topic, thereby substantially enriching the dark pattern scholarship by capturing relevant contextual and peripheral debates.

⁹² See eg Dickinson (n 86) 1647-1648; Leiser, M.R. and Caruana, M. (n 93) 6; Alison Hung (n 55) 2498-2501. According to our findings, the extent to which the market power of platforms (designers) influences the deployment of dark patterns and the structure of market competition remains unsettled in the legal literature. We discuss this in Section 6.1.2

⁹³ Jeremy Wiener, 'Deceptive Design and Ongoing Consent in Privacy Law' (2021) 53 *Ottawa Law Review* 133; Gray and others, 'Dark Patterns and the Legal Requirements of Consent Banners' (n 29); Lapin and Volungevičiūtė (n 44); Haley (n 80).

⁹⁴ Wagner and others (n 41).

⁹⁵ Leiser, M.R. and Caruana, M. (n 93) 6.

fundamental level.⁹⁶ Others discuss how dark design patterns in games (e.g., 'loot boxes') resemble real-world unrestricted gambling,⁹⁷ and how these design mechanisms could lead to similar negative externalities in society.⁹⁸

In sum, Section 5.2 outlines legal researchers' contemporary understandings of dark patterns and their treatment of the subject in legal study. It identifies a shared knowledge foundation for future collaboration (e.g., root problems and diverse harms) while highlighting areas of divergence for further dialogue, to be discussed in Section 6.

5.3. Laws, doctrinal challenges, and pathways for reform discussed to regulate dark patterns

This section provides a comprehensive mapping of the regulatory landscape of dark patterns by grouping the laws concerning dark patterns, as discussed in the scholarship, into different seven clusters.⁹⁹ As shown in Figure 7, *protection and privacy law*(n=27)¹⁰⁰ and *consumer protection law*(n=27)¹⁰¹ are widely recognised as crucial for regulating dark patterns, with *theory of law* is less frequently discussed (each n=3). A small number of *other laws* are seen as viable regulatory tools for reining in dark patterns (n=12), such as gambling law, intellectual property law, tort law (including product liability law), financial law, health insurance law, and corporate law. This section also examines the regulation of dark patterns by sorting the doctrinal problems of the laws (Section 5.3.1) and systematically compiling the proposed solutions of various scales scattered across the papers (Section 5.3.2)

⁹⁶ Marks (n 57); Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64).

⁹⁷ Xiao (n 90).

⁹⁸ Sheldon A. Evans (n 43).

⁹⁹ Codes are generally distributed non-exclusively, except in the case of papers that engage solely with theoretical discussions without identifiable regulations. Accordingly, the presentation of content analysis is provided in absolute numbers rather than percentages. The classification of the clusters of laws is based on the major functions of the laws and specifically the shared primary objective and social purposes. Such functionalism also makes different regulations and legislations across jurisdictions more comparable, as they all focus on the regulation of dark patterns. See Ralf Michaels, 'The Functional Method of Comparative Law' in Mathias Reimann and Reinhard Zimmermann (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Comparative Law* (Oxford University Press 2006) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199296064.013.0011>> accessed 27 February 2025.

¹⁰⁰ For example, General Data Protection Regulation (including the previous Directive) and the e-Privacy Directive (including the proposed regulation), the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act, the California Consumer Privacy Act, the California Privacy Rights Act, and the Colorado Consumer Privacy Act are categorised as data protection and privacy laws.

¹⁰¹ For example, the Online Users Reduction (DETOUR) Act and the Unfair Commercial Practice Directive, Consumer Rights Directive are categorised as consumer protection laws.

Figure 7: Regulations mainly discussed.

5.3.1. Doctrinal challenges of the corresponding laws¹⁰²

The fuzzy boundaries between concepts (Theories of law)

Only three papers engage purely with theories of law without identifiable legislation (n=3). They collectively reflect an unresolved and foundational challenge in distinguishing between closely related concepts, such as persuasion, manipulation, deception, coercion, and similar concepts. For example, it is pointed out that regulators must make difficult decisions regarding where the line lies precisely between these concepts in the context of dark design patterns to eliminate problematic conduct from the market without overregulation.¹⁰³ Although dark patterns are commonly recognised as having crossed the line of proper persuasion, scholars approach the conundrum of concepts differently.

Some researchers define manipulation as hidden influences, including deception, as opposed to overt influences like persuasion and coercion.¹⁰⁴ Others predominantly focus on the complexity of persuasion and manipulation,¹⁰⁵ or examine deception and dark patterns with a deceptive nature to avoid the issue of when marketing becomes unfair or abusive manipulation.¹⁰⁶ Some view dark patterns as coercions forcing users to spend attention, data, and money in the digital economy, exploring when persuasive and manipulative design becomes coercive in digital market competition.¹⁰⁷ These inconsistent approaches increase the difficulty in capturing the

¹⁰² 'Doctrinal challenges' is used to refer to theoretical challenges in a legal sense, for the benefit of general readers.

¹⁰³ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29) 46.

¹⁰⁴ Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64). See also Spencer (n 47).

¹⁰⁵ Calo (n 75).

¹⁰⁶ Lauren E. Willis (n 71).

¹⁰⁷ Day and Stemler (n 68) 34.

nature of dark patterns, which is plausibly vital for normative evaluation (See Section 6.1.1.) and results in equivocal use of terms (e.g., ‘deceptive designs/patterns’ or ‘manipulative designs/patterns’) or ‘dark patterns’.

The problem of the types and levels of ‘harm’ (Theories of law)

When the conceptual boundaries between legitimate persuasion and problematic manipulation, deception, and coercion are unclear, evaluating the harm of dark patterns becomes challenging. For example, researchers believe that under the current US regulatory framework, many mild dark patterns (e.g., in advertisements) appear not to violate existing policies.¹⁰⁸ When dark patterns are subtle, traditional protective doctrines for consumers (such as duress, mistake, undue influence, misrepresentation, or *culpa in contrahendo*) are inadequate to address these issues,¹⁰⁹ as they neither make false statements nor omit material facts. They are not considered unfair as they are essentially avoidable, while the harm may be too minor to warrant limited regulatory resources.¹¹⁰ The difficulty in differentiating minor harm from harms that merit legal intervention poses an obstacle for existing laws to curb harms from certain dark patterns (e.g., nagging).¹¹¹

A similar lack of consensus exists in the EU.¹¹² It is pointed out that promising legislation addressing dark patterns (the DSA,¹¹³ GDPR,¹¹⁴ UCPD)¹¹⁵ does not provide applicable criteria to quantify harms, nor have further guidelines been issued on this matter, which hampers effective and predictable administrative decisions and individual remedies in civil proceedings. Similarly, in the EU’s scenario of ‘substantial injury’, dark patterns in violation of EU data protection law

¹⁰⁸ Eric Zeng and others, ‘Polls, Clickbait, and Commemorative \$2 Bills: Problematic Political Advertising on News and Media Websites around the 2020 U.S. Elections’, *Proceedings of the 21st ACM Internet Measurement Conference* (ACM 2021) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3487552.3487850>> accessed 9 December 2023.

¹⁰⁹ Martin Ebers, ‘Liability For Artificial Intelligence And EU Consumer Law’ (2021) 12 *Journal of Intellectual Property, Information Technology and E-Commerce Law* 204, 210.

¹¹⁰ Calo (n 75) 1043.

¹¹¹ Alison Hung (n 55) 2506–2508.

¹¹² Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara (n 9).

¹¹³ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act) (PE/30/2022/REV/1), OJ L 277/1 (DSA).

¹¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) OJ L 119/1 (GDPR).

¹¹⁵ Directive 2005/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2005 concerning unfair business-to-consumer commercial practices in the internal market and amending Council Directive 84/450/EEC, Directives 97/7/EC, 98/27/EC and 2002/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council (‘Unfair Commercial Practices Directive’) (Text with EEA relevance) OJ L 149/1 (UCPD).

face disparities at the national court level regarding whether remedies for 'non-material damage' should adhere to a *de minimis* damage threshold.

The problematic dichotomy of average and vulnerable consumers (Consumer protection law)

While there is a comparable amount of research from a consumer protection perspective (n=27), we find that empirical studies on dark patterns from a consumer welfare protection perspective are less explored¹¹⁶ and a convergence of legal scholars' opinions that the dichotomy of consumers stills present a problem. For example, it is pointed out that, when dark patterns are backed by profiling and algorithmic personalisation and go beyond uniform UI choice architecture, the outdated dichotomy of average and vulnerable consumers in consumer protection laws is identified as the crux. Building on the previous section on bounded rationality, it is increasingly recognised that the vulnerabilities of individual consumers may also be *contextual* and *influenced by external factors*, leading to the obsolescence of the traditional consumer protection rationale.¹¹⁷ When dark patterns are supported by group or individual algorithmic profiling, the distinction between average and vulnerable consumers dissolves, making every consumer vulnerable as accurate detection (and even incubation) and exploitation of vulnerabilities can be easily achieved.¹¹⁸

In the US, the fall of the traditional consumer dichotomy presents significant challenges in courts. The assumptions of 'a reasonable consumer' and 'expert facial analysis' methods, such as usability tests for assessing digital interface deceptiveness, struggle with the personalised nature of algorithmic marketing, which tailors services and presentations to individuals 'in a world of one-to-one marketing', eliminating the notion of a standardised reasonable consumer.¹¹⁹ Presumably the EU may face the same conundrum, as the UCPD guidance¹²⁰ has acknowledged that consumer vulnerabilities are dynamic and situational,¹²¹ moving away from rigid categorisations based on internal characteristics. However, it is still unclear how courts will practically assess the vulnerabilities of consumers facing evolving and personalised dark patterns.

¹¹⁶ These differences in numbers also speak to Gray's findings that many empirical studies predominantly focus on the functionality of consent banners while subscriptions were far less commonly studied. Gray and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship' (n 13) 189.

¹¹⁷ Fassiaux (n 45); Martin Ebers (n 112); Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64).

¹¹⁸ Calo (n 75) 1034; Silvia De Conca (n 54) 11; Faraoni (n 59).

¹¹⁹ Lauren E. Willis (n 71) 154–157.

¹²⁰ Commission Notice – Guidance on the interpretation and application of Directive 2005/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning unfair business-to-consumer commercial practices in the internal market C/2021/9320 OJ C 526/1 (UCPD Guidance 2021).

¹²¹ UCPD Guidance 2021, 100.

The problem of the consent mechanism & individual approach to data regulation (Data protection and privacy law)

In the realm of data protection and privacy law, one of the most explored areas in the corpus (n=27), topics of dark patterns in consent management interfaces and their effects dominate empirical studies. The over-reliance on consent mechanisms has been criticised from many aspects. A convincing point is that, even without dark patterns, the mere repetition of dealing with different consent interfaces daily leads to consent fatigue, which undermines the informed consent mechanism intended by legislators ('fatigue by design').¹²² This consent fatigue is damaging, as companies can circumvent consent with even minor dark patterns.¹²³ Others reiterate the indifference to the bounded rationality issue in data protection law, as policymakers fall into the 'consent fallacy', assuming people would always make decisions rationally and in their best interest with the provided information. However, people do not possess unbounded rationality, nor can they manage the full burden of information flows on data practices thoroughly, while the proliferation of dark patterns pushes the limits of the consent approach.¹²⁴

The outdated theory of competition law, misposition of platform power (Competition Law)

Among our corpus, 12 papers discussed competition law, however, non adopted empirical approaches. Even under this uneven exploration, the problems of competition law identified are more diverse. O'Loughlin introduces the concept of 'cognitive foreclosure' and challenges the traditional rationale of competition law, highlighting how behavioural economics and the evidential effectiveness of dark patterns challenge the "strict rationality" assumption underlying competition law and question the derivative theory of efficient entry and switching related to the self-correcting capacities of markets.¹²⁵ Critics argue that outdated competition law theories result in a myopia regarding artificially high prices, thereby failing to promote privacy as a component of consumer welfare. This failure allows the proliferation of online manipulation by tech companies that adopt a free and low-price business model.¹²⁶ The outdated theories also

¹²² Gerald Spindler and Lydia Förster, 'Privacy-Compliant Design of Cookie Banners According to the GDPR' (2023) 14 *Journal of Intellectual Property, Information Technology and E-Commerce Law* 2, 27; Haley (n 80) 75; Christie Dougherty, 'Every Breath You Take, Every Move You Make, Facebook's Watching You: A Behavioral Economic Analysis of the US California Consumer Privacy Act and EU ePrivacy Regulation' (2020) 12 *Northeastern University Law Review* 629, 659.

¹²³ Alison Hung (n 55).

¹²⁴ Sanju Ahuja and Jyoti Kumar, 'Conceptualizations of User Autonomy within the Normative Evaluation of Dark Patterns' (2022) 24 *Ethics and Information Technology* 52; MR Leiser, "'Dark Patterns': The Case for Regulatory Pluralism between the European Union's Consumer and Data Protection Regimes' in E. Kosta and others (eds), *Research Handbook on EU Data Protection Law* (2022); Susser, Roessler and Nissenbaum (n 64).

¹²⁵ O'Loughlin (n 70).

¹²⁶ Day and Stemler (n 68).

lead to a mispositioning of information service platforms, creating inappropriate safe harbour exemptions for the main sources of consumer manipulation in the digital era.¹²⁷ In sum, without a theoretical review, current competition law struggles to protect consumers from dark patterns and other forms of digital manipulation.

The new shadow cast by AI (DSA and AIA)

Compared to the aforementioned regulatory regimes, only a few papers (n=7) examine potential loopholes in the EU digital strategy package, despite many highlighting its potential to regulate dark patterns.¹²⁸ A key emerging issue is whether the new laws can competently address dark patterns influenced or driven by AI. Cohen criticises the EU AI Act's¹²⁹ overemphasis on subliminal techniques, which are non-perceptible and highly ambiguous.¹³⁰ The scholar argues that the real issue with manipulative AI involves attention distraction and awareness deprivation. Such abilities of AI share similarities with the essential characteristics of current dark patterns that manipulate human attentional processes, and AI can 'purposefully pull a viewer's attention toward certain visual stimuli to prevent them from attending to others,' blurring the line between unattended and imperceptible, and leading to an unreliable boundary between subliminal and non-subliminal techniques.

More importantly, this ability of AI aligns with the basic logic behind dark design patterns on websites. With the power of machine learning models, dark patterns are expected to evolve into uniform dark patterns targeting the most susceptible (vulnerable) times, or 'dynamically personalise a digital environment based on individual-level biases and vulnerabilities to inattention'.¹³¹ Therefore, Cohen argues that the transparency requirements in the AI Act and the DSA fall short since they might expose outright manipulative intent, but do not fully address manipulative stimuli.¹³²

Fundamental rights: The right to autonomy and commercial speech

As the harm of dark patterns to autonomy is widely recognised (See Section 5.2.4.1), some scholars argue that the absence of a fundamental right to autonomy hinders its protection

¹²⁷ Stemler, Perry and Haugh (n 46).

¹²⁸ See eg Silvia De Conca (n 54); Faraoni (n 59); Maximilian Gartner, 'Regulatory Acknowledgment of Individual Autonomy in European Digital Legislation: From Meta-Principle to Explicit Protection in the Data Act' (2022) 8 European Data Protection Law Review 462.

¹²⁹ European Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council, 'Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts' COM (2021) 206 final.

¹³⁰ Cohen (n 43).

¹³¹ *ibid* 223–224.

¹³² *ibid* 233.

against dark patterns.¹³³ Both internationally and in Europe, there is a lack of consensus on which fundamental rights are violated by computational manipulation and which rights could protect individuals against such abuses, leading to calls for these rights to be explicitly defined in legislation to offer better protection against enhanced dark patterns.¹³⁴ Conversely, a regulatory challenge frequently cited in the US is the First Amendment's protection of commercial speech.¹³⁵ The proposed DETOUR Act, aimed specifically at dark patterns, and similar regulations might be obstructed by First Amendment protections, provided the commercial speech is not deemed misleading.¹³⁶ However, as discussed in earlier sections on concepts and harms, many subtle and non-deceptive dark patterns can elude the 'misleading' threshold. Consequently, companies remain an advantage in rendering the First Amendment as a shield against the regulation of dark patterns.¹³⁷

The contradiction in contracts (Contract Law)

Discussions on contract law (n=5) mainly focus on the theory of contracting which questions the nature of consent to privacy policies concerning dark patterns.¹³⁸ The efficacy of regulating dark patterns through contract law is ambiguous.¹³⁹ While some scholars argue that contracts involving dark patterns should be considered invalid because mutual assent is manipulated, the blurred boundaries between concepts still raise questions about whether contract law can guide judges in navigating these issues.¹⁴⁰ Moreover, the level of 'harm' still needs more empirical evidence to buttress the courts' decisions against dark patterns in contracting.¹⁴¹ Other critics centre the contract law doctrine, advocating for a re-evaluation of the 'freedom of contract' principle in light of how dark patterns infiltrate and secure platform-dictated standard form consumer contracts, exacerbating power imbalances and undermining the principle's original

¹³³ Lin Kyi and others, 'Investigating Deceptive Design in GDPR's Legitimate Interest', *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Association for Computing Machinery 2023) <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3580637>>.

¹³⁴ Faraoni (n 59) 11; Gartner (n 131) 472; Ahuja and Kumar (n 127). Gartner suggests that while explicitly defining a fundamental right to autonomy could enhance individual protection against dark patterns, the current phrasing in the Data Act and other European data strategy legislation already implies this right through existing human rights, such as data protection and privacy. Comparatively, Ahuja and Kumar argue that policy should differentiate between conditional and ideal autonomy, the latter being defined by law.

¹³⁵ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 80); Calo (n 75); Alison Hung (n 55).

¹³⁶ Dougherty (n 125) 656.

¹³⁷ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29) 100–101; Garon (n 63) 210.

¹³⁸ Haley (n 80).

¹³⁹ Here, we observed mixed opinions. For example, Dickinson (2023, p.1661) claims that private laws including tort law and contract law can remedy dark patterns sufficiently with other existing regulatory frameworks.

¹⁴⁰ Martin Ebers (n 112) 210.

¹⁴¹ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29) 92–93.

intent.¹⁴² Furthermore, the private law nature of contract law perpetuates the ineffective individual regulatory model, in which consumers either fail to realise that they are being manipulated or tend to tolerate the cost and burden of exercising their rights through litigation, especially when class actions are prima facie foreclosed by an arbitration clause.¹⁴³

Limitations of the current soft law and self-regulation

The regulation of dark patterns outside binding laws is rarely discussed, with scholars highlighting the absence of clear guidelines. Academics find it challenging to derive practical guidelines (i.e., precise specifications regarding the concrete design of digital consent tools) from complex regulations. This difficulty has led to widespread legal non-compliance, such as with cookie banners,¹⁴⁴ and it fosters environments that accommodate dark patterns in privacy policies.¹⁴⁵ Thus, more legal intervention is deemed necessary to foster multi-dimensional solutions, as relying on industry self-regulation is impractical due to economic conflicts of interest.¹⁴⁶ Where soft laws are in place, their effectiveness is often questioned. Empirical studies show that self-regulatory measures, like warning labels in video games, are unreliable, especially on mobile platforms.¹⁴⁷ Consent Management Platforms (CMPs) that follow the self-regulatory transparency and Consent Framework (TCF) by IAB Europe may fail to comply with data protection laws, with some enabling the customisation of dark patterns, undermining their intended purpose.¹⁴⁸

5.3.2. Revisions of regulation proposed to solve dark patterns

This section focuses on theming, from the corpus, concrete proposals for refining regulations or providing actionable solutions to dark patterns. Compared to the underlying doctrinal challenges that lack straightforward solutions, as elaborated above, it is noted that many proposed solutions are not tied to a specific legal domain. This may shed light on possible paradigm shifts for the future regulation of dark patterns, which are explored in the Discussion section.

5.3.2.1. Proposal 1: Paradigmatic changes of legal doctrines

Various scholars propose paradigm changes in legal doctrines to better address the challenges of dark patterns and other digital manipulations. Among these, some advocate for a *lex specialis*,

¹⁴² Kristin B Cornelius, 'Zombie Contracts, Dark Patterns of Design, and "Documentisation"' (2019) 8 Internet Policy Review.

¹⁴³ Stemler, Perry and Haugh (n 46) 650.

¹⁴⁴ Gerald Spindler and Lydia Förster (n 125) 3.

¹⁴⁵ Kyi and others (n 136).

¹⁴⁶ Bongard-Blanchy and others (n 6).

¹⁴⁷ Xiao (n 90).

¹⁴⁸ Habib and others (n 41).

specifically targeting dark patterns. The proposed US Deceptive Experiences to Online Users Reduction (DETOUR) Act aims to curb manipulative dark pattern behaviour by prohibiting large online platforms from using user interfaces that intentionally impair user autonomy, decision-making, or choice.¹⁴⁹ The bill encourages promising regulatory initiatives, such as empowering the FTC to support a registered standard body that issues guidelines for platform design practices, overseeing platforms' routine disclosure of behavioural experiments, and establishing independent review boards.¹⁵⁰ Griffin similarly proposes a specialised law targeting manipulative designs by 'systemically important platforms', introducing protective default settings, enhanced user controls through service feature disaggregation (e.g., disabling loot boxes and timed regenerations in games), and imposing extra taxes on manipulative design practices.¹⁵¹

Another approach involves updating competition law theories and follow-up policies to control platform powers. Marks introduces the concept of 'biopower' and discusses how platforms harness biopower through unregulated conglomerates, concentric mergers, and surveillance control networks to influence social norms.¹⁵² He advocates for expanding the 'consumer welfare' concept and revitalising merger control to collectively evaluate data flows, biopower, and coercive choice architectures, including dark patterns. O'Loughlin introduces 'cognitive foreclosure', highlighting how dark patterns by large platforms lead to market failures that justify anticompetitive intervention.¹⁵³ Day and Stemler argue that dark patterns and other online manipulations lead to anticompetitive effects akin to supra-competitive pricing, suggesting that recognising the cost of such harm to consumer autonomy as a reflection of market quality justifies using competition law against dark patterns.¹⁵⁴

Contract law and the duty of fiduciary are also viewed as promising approaches to regulate dark patterns. When traditional rules on duress and misrepresentation fall short, some researchers believe that the doctrine of undue influence in contract law offers a viable solution.¹⁵⁵ However, they note that the relational domination between platforms and consumers may hinder this approach, which could be addressed by recognising 'fiduciary duties of platforms to consumers'. Supported by Hartzog & Richards, this proposal advocates for imposing 'a duty of data loyalty' on platforms, shifting the regulatory focus from proving individual harm to addressing the power

¹⁴⁹ Mark Warner (n 90) 8.

¹⁵⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁵¹ Caleb N Griffin, 'Systemically Important Platforms' 107 445.

¹⁵² Marks (n 57) 523.

¹⁵³ See n 125

¹⁵⁴ See n 126

¹⁵⁵ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29).

imbalance and imposing more duties on platforms.¹⁵⁶ Similarly focusing on the imbalanced relationship, Willis advocates for reversing the burden of proof, suggesting a judicial default presumption when consumers hold false beliefs material to a transaction, assuming the business stands to benefit, and broadening the definition of 'unfair practices' to include any exploitation of consumer confusion for profit.¹⁵⁷

In terms of consumer protection and data privacy laws, there is a growing demand to expand the application of the fairness principle beyond individual decision-making moments. Leiser advocates for a broader approach to tackling dark patterns through a specialised Code of Conduct, potentially extending beyond the UCPD's scope, promoting a shift towards 'fairness-by-design' to hold designers accountable.¹⁵⁸ Additionally, linking the fairness principle from the UCPD to the GDPR, researchers urge lawmakers to analyse the overall system architecture, UX, and UI more holistically rather than merely simplifying consent procedures.¹⁵⁹ Similarly, Wiener argues that privacy law should treat consent as an ongoing agency process, with assessments of unfair designs extending beyond mere agreement moments to encompass all interactions.¹⁶⁰

5.3.2.2. Proposal 2: Refining the existing regulatory frameworks¹⁶¹

Beyond macro paradigm shifts, there are calls for refining statutes and strengthening enforcement. Given the historically weak enforcement of consumer protection law, following the proposed Dark Pattern Code of Conduct under the UCPD framework,¹⁶² Leiser advocates for establishing clearer boundaries between allowable and non-allowable commercial practices via a two-criteria assessment and creating a blacklist for unacceptable dark patterns. In the US, efforts are focused on empowering the FTC. Wilson explores the FTC's potential to promulgate rules that explicitly define and prohibit dark patterns under Section 18 of the FTC Act.¹⁶³ He also suggests amending the Restore Online Shoppers' Confidence Act (ROSCA) to broaden its scope, thereby enhancing the FTC's ability to regulate dark patterns. Furthermore, there are suggestions that the FTC could better utilise consent decrees as a tool for ongoing supervision

¹⁵⁶ Hartzog and Richards (n 76) 1031.

¹⁵⁷ Lauren E. Willis (n 71) 119.

¹⁵⁸ Mark Leiser and Wen-Ting Yang (n 81).

¹⁵⁹ MR Leiser (n 127) 248.

¹⁶⁰ Wiener (n 96) 169.

¹⁶¹ Since we do not imply design ethics as calls for self-regulation unless researchers articulate the stance to promote it as a regulation approach, we find few papers that substantially propose solely self-regulation. Rather, appeals for more support from regulators and policymakers remain mainstream. The only exception is Hurwitz (n 62).

¹⁶² See n 158

¹⁶³ Wilson (n 40).

of companies post initial violations of Section 5, ensuring more stringent and consistent oversight of dark patterns.¹⁶⁴

To bolster enforcement, many researchers argue that empirical studies and insights from HCI practitioners should play a larger role in regulatory discussions. For instance, empirical data on the effectiveness of various dark patterns could inform enforcement priorities and help define the line between permissible and impermissible practices.¹⁶⁵ Scholars propose that HCI researchers contribute to regulation by developing flexible taxonomies of dark patterns and automating detection methods for quicker violation checks.¹⁶⁶ Moreover, the effectiveness of laws and soft laws against dark patterns should be periodically reassessed through empirical legal research.¹⁶⁷ Meanwhile, it is proposed that regulators should consider collaboration with HCI designers, such as developing user-centred CMPs or setting up evidence-based design criteria, ensuring that only compliant CMPs enter the market.¹⁶⁸

5.3.2.3. Proposal 3: Technical design-embedded solution and design accountability check

Possible solutions include not only amendments to legislation or new regulatory frameworks but also certain technical solutions positioned as a form of regulation. For example, dark pattern detection is a significant contribution from HCI,¹⁶⁹ involving enhanced taxonomies of dark patterns used as criteria or integrated into automated detection systems. Mathur et al. suggest outsourcing the identification and flagging of dark patterns to the public, aiding the development of countermeasures like dark pattern blockers and machine-learning-based automatic detection systems.¹⁷⁰

Others address system and function redesign to combat dark patterns at their core. O'Connor et al. concentrate on redesigning the opt-out mechanisms for data protection and privacy laws, advocating for more conspicuous opt-out mechanisms for personal information sales that go

¹⁶⁴ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29) 98–99. Other ideas on expanding the remit of the FTC are also proposed by Sylvain (2022) who calls for the FTC to take over the responsibility that is failed by the FCC and the Telecommunications Act, regarding protecting consumers from deceptive and manipulative practices by consumer-facing information services.

¹⁶⁵ *ibid* 48.

¹⁶⁶ Thomas Mildner and others, 'Defending Against the Dark Arts: Recognising Dark Patterns in Social Media' (Association for Computing Machinery 2023) 2372 <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3563657.3595964>>.

¹⁶⁷ n 147

¹⁶⁸ Midas Nouwens and others, 'Dark Patterns after the GDPR: Scraping Consent Pop-Ups and Demonstrating Their Influence', *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2020) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3313831.3376321>> accessed 19 January 2024.

¹⁶⁹ Papers that incorporate discussions on detection and policing are limited in number in our corpus, as they are seen as appendages to the substantial regulatory discussions which our review focuses on.

¹⁷⁰ Mathur and others (n 41).

beyond a simple link to comply with the CCPA.¹⁷¹ Comparatively, Spindler and Forster explore embedding the Do-Not-Track function within software and browsers to enhance user control over personal data sharing with online services and propose 'button labelling' solutions as counter-nudges against dark patterns.¹⁷² They specifically propose the deployment of a 'Personal Information Management System' (PIMS). This system would allow users to manage and update all privacy settings for various service providers via a central dashboard, complemented by an auxiliary data fiduciary framework. Such a system could address several persistent consent issues that facilitate dark patterns (e.g., consent fatigue, difficult-to-opt-out).

In addition to direct system redesign, some researchers explore frameworks for UX design accountability. Targeting the generally poor opt-out design for data sharing, Gunawan et al. suggest a checking process on design feature parity to help enforcement agencies assess the balance of UX design 'beyond opt-in/opt-out requests, and across modalities'.¹⁷³ On the other hand, Wagner et al. believe that the German enforcement authority's 'procedural accountability' approach to Facebook's dark patterns is a promising prototype, through transparency and accountability requirements.¹⁷⁴ According to their construct, this procedural accountability check involves regulators requiring details on how a task is handled, which further triggers the oversight mechanism regarding the design of the business processes, workflows, and technologies by external or internal relevant parties (e.g., regulators and users).

Furthermore, when discussing 'dark patterns' in the context of rhetoric and visuals in standard-form documents, proposed solutions also involve strong technical reshaping. Cornelius advocates for the adoption of document engineering for standard form consumer contracts (including privacy and cookie policies) (SFCCs), emphasising principles like standardisation, documentation, and explanation.¹⁷⁵ This involves comprehensive documentation of the presentation, design, and content of documents to ensure they are preservable/scrapable, trackable/stable, authentic/reliable, and processable, supporting informed public discussion and balancing power asymmetries.¹⁷⁶ Similarly, Seuchter et al. call for systematic cookie-policy documentation and management, advocating for machine-readable cookie policies that can be

¹⁷¹ Sean O'Connor and others, '(Un)Clear and (In)Conspicuous: The Right to Opt-out of Sale under CCPA', *Proceedings of the 20th Workshop on Privacy in the Electronic Society* (ACM 2021) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3463676.3485598>> accessed 19 January 2024.

¹⁷² Gerald Spindler and Lydia Förster (n 125).

¹⁷³ Johanna Gunawan and others (n 37) 377:23.

¹⁷⁴ Wagner and others (n 41) 266.

¹⁷⁵ Cornelius (n 145).

¹⁷⁶ *ibid* 5.

standardised and presented consistently, with version control allowing for archived cookie policy checks.¹⁷⁷

Finally, a highly popular technical solution among HCI researchers is a browser-based approach to dark patterns, especially concerning privacy and personal data protection. A browser-level consent management interface is viewed as a sustainable solution that automates user consent decisions, significantly reducing consent fatigue and effectively addressing dark patterns in cookie banners.¹⁷⁸ This approach could provide a scalable opt-out solution when integrated with 'Do not sell' signals, replacing inherently flawed individual opt-out methods.¹⁷⁹ Additionally, standardised, machine-readable cookie policies displayed via browsers would enable users to better understand and manage their consent.¹⁸⁰ For consumer protection beyond data privacy, browser-level solutions could incorporate community-supported automated dark pattern detection and blocking plugins.¹⁸¹

6. Discussion

In this section, based on the findings, we discuss the factors that inherently obstruct the establishment of a comprehensive regulatory framework to combat dark patterns. We select the most essential and constructive ideas from the sampled literature that support our arguments. We argue that the inherent ambiguities in the concept of 'dark patterns' – its nature, harms, and scope – present significant barriers to crafting mature and practical regulations (Section 6.1). Later, we explore how suggested technical solutions, accountability frameworks, and practical design guidelines could lead to more promising regulatory strategies (Section 6.2). Taking a step further, we discuss the possible new regulatory paradigm stressing diligent designs that go beyond the harm-proving impasse (Section 6.3), and future research opportunities that necessitate interdisciplinary collaboration (Section 6.4).

6.1. Factors that hinder the establishment of a comprehensive regulatory framework

6.1.1. The normative 'nature' problem

We believe that current regulations are hindered by the ambiguous nature of diverse types of dark patterns. As specified previously, the extent to which dark patterns are persuasive, manipulative, deceptive, or coercive is not well-defined. However, clarifying the normative nature of different dark patterns is crucial as they underpin the existing regulatory framework.

¹⁷⁷ Seuchter and others (n 84).

¹⁷⁸ Nouwens and others (n 155) See Habib and others (n 24); Kyi and others (n 90).

¹⁷⁹ O'Connor and others (n 174).

¹⁸⁰ Seuchter and others (n 84).

¹⁸¹ Mathur and others (n 41).

Consumer protection law depends on interpreting deception (e.g., ‘misleading commercial practices’ in the UCPD¹⁸² and ‘deceptive acts or practices’ in the FTC Act)¹⁸³ and, to some extent, coercion (‘aggressive commercial practices’ in the UCPD¹⁸⁴ and ‘unfair acts or practices’ in the FTC Act).¹⁸⁵ Moreover, interpreting coercion is essential for justifying interventions under competition law. Unfortunately, despite frequent references to ‘manipulative’ or ‘deceptive designs’ as synonyms for dark patterns, explicit concept differentiation is lacking in existing laws addressing dark patterns, creating a barrier to regulation.

Several factors may have contributed to this normative ambiguity. Firstly, even theoretically, the differentiation between these concepts remains unresolved. Secondly, dark patterns, by nature, constitute a collective and thematic concept;¹⁸⁶ some types may be deceptive (e.g., sneaking into baskets, disguised ads) while others are coercive (e.g., nagging). More importantly, considering the rapid evolution and diversification of dark patterns, case-by-case determination of their normative nature, especially in an *ex post* regulatory paradigm, could increase the burden on regulatory resources. Thirdly, the accumulation of various dark patterns throughout UX design could complicate distinguishing their nature. When reviewed against the backdrop of more advanced dark pattern forms (e.g. personalised dark patterns, dark patterns on conversational UIs), this distinction becomes even more obscure.

Consequently, the unsettled nature of dark patterns complicates regulation. Further research could enrich the normative discussion by, for example, discussing the differences between ‘coercion’ as a simple design feature (e.g., nagging) and as a contextual barrier to switching services (e.g., the lock-in effect), or even as the absence of better-designed alternatives (e.g., a shift in social norms), and explore how laws (e.g., consumer protection, competition, human rights) might coordinate with each other on these understandings. Nonetheless, it might be more pertinent to question whether rigidly categorising design patterns into traditional legislative structures could achieve effective regulatory outcomes, especially when these legal frameworks may themselves require re-evaluation in the digital era. Therefore, a regulatory approach to dark patterns that rigidly assigns fixed normative labels to each identifiable type may not be practical. Regulatory discussions could benefit from exploring a more holistic concept of ‘unfairness’ and ‘unfair patterns’ (potentially through more *ex-ante* paradigms), which could encompass all unfair influences without becoming stalled at the preliminary phase of

¹⁸² Articles 6 and 7, UCPD.

¹⁸³ Section 5, Federal Trade Commission Act (FTC Act) 1914 s 5

¹⁸⁴ Article 8 and 9, UCPD

¹⁸⁵ n 183

¹⁸⁶ Mathur, Kshirsagar and Mayer (n 4).

concept subdivision.¹⁸⁷ This proposed approach speaks to the current ‘blacklist’ approach in UCPD, but is also likely to be adopted and take the form of practical guidance on dark pattern restrictions under specific laws, including DSA, DMA and Data Act. Building upon these insights, we also discuss another concept (i.e., diligent designs) that could be useful in Section 6.3.

6.1.2. The ‘harms’ problem

We argue that the regulation of dark patterns that solely relies on demonstrating harms would be difficult to enforce. This is because, firstly, as already shown by our findings, current regulations on dark patterns struggle due to the difficulty in identifying evident and actionable harm. The blurred line between acceptable persuasion and unacceptable dark patterns complicates the classification of harm severity and the determination of which levels merit legal remedies. While harm types may seem clear, it is important to note that, aside from financial harm, other types are intangible harms that are difficult to quantify and demonstrate. This difficulty in addressing dark patterns through a harm-based approach in judicial proceedings is already evident in, for example, the concerning absence of damage claims in GDPR case law, despite the potential severity of dark pattern harms,¹⁸⁸ Additionally, there is a scarcity of case law addressing mild dark patterns (e.g., hidden costs)¹⁸⁹ even when they involve financial harm, which should be easier to measure and prove than other types of harms. In essence, basing the regulation of dark patterns on the demonstration of quantifiable and evident harm may hinder the development of practical and comprehensive regulation.

Secondly, some theories of harm proposed by scholars are controversial and would hinder effective regulation of dark patterns from the start. A salient discrepancy we observe lies in scholars’ differing beliefs about how dark patterns harm competition and consumer welfare. Some emphasise the role of platforms with market power, arguing that their dominance transforms mild design patterns from mere persuasion into coercion and market abuse. This manipulation steers users towards suboptimal behaviours, creating cognitive foreclosure and consumer-side market failures that harm consumer welfare and market competition.¹⁹⁰ Conversely, other researchers argue that market power might be irrelevant, and that the use of dark patterns may not significantly impact market competition. They suggest that dark patterns,

¹⁸⁷ This would raise questions about the concept of ‘unfairness’ (similarly, ‘fairness’), which needs to be evaluated against the culture and expectations within the community that is influenced by the most pertinent dark pattern forms. In this sense, sector-based empirical evaluation of ‘(un)fair’ designs could be indispensable.

¹⁸⁸ Johanna Gunawan, Cristiana Santos, and Irene Kamara (n 9).

¹⁸⁹ Mark Leiser and Wen-Ting Yang (n 81) 513.

¹⁹⁰ Day and Stemler (n 68). O’Loughlin (n 70).

although subtle, effectively steer consumer decisions without necessarily causing backlash.¹⁹¹ Consumer biases are so easily exploited that firms typically focus on capitalising on these biases and vulnerabilities rather than competing to ‘debias consumers’, leading to a ‘race to the bottom’ in market competition.¹⁹²

We believe that such varying interpretations of harm to market competition and consumer welfare limit the regulatory capacity to address dark patterns, especially from a competition law angle. This issue is even more concerning because, under either theory, consumer welfare remains at risk, regardless of the difficulty in proving contested anti-competitive effects. Therefore, we advocate for a theoretical update of competition law theories. This is because, from a traditional competition law perspective, if consumer protection is considered secondary to market competition protection, the remedial potential of competition law against dark patterns remains limited. Nevertheless, an interesting area for further research is the implications of the EU Digital Markets Act (DMA),¹⁹³ which does not directly address the causal relationship between protected values but notably imposes an ex-ante ban on interface designs by gatekeepers that could undermine the effectiveness of the prohibitions and obligations specified in the Act.¹⁹⁴ This aligns with our findings on how dark patterns harm the functions of law in Section 5.2.4.3. Therefore, the DMA appears to acknowledge that manipulating user decision-making through dark patterns by entities with significant market power (‘gatekeepers’) would reduce contestability in the digital market, which in itself warrants regulation.

Consequently, the regulation of dark patterns that solely relies on proving harm would have to tackle both the challenge of establishing evident and actionable harm and the uncertainty surrounding harm theories before envisaging a robust legal framework.

6.1.3. The ‘scope’ problem

The functioning of current regulations is impacted by the expanding scope of the dark patterns concept in legal scholarship (See Section 5.2.2). We believe that this expansion could be significant but also poses risks that might affect the regulatory landscape for two reasons.

Firstly, an expanding scope of dark patterns could dilute their distinctiveness, potentially merging the term with the broader context of online/digital manipulation. Originally, ‘dark patterns’ referred primarily to surface-level UI manipulations; the strong initial focus might

¹⁹¹ Luguri and Strahilevitz (n 29).

¹⁹² Lirio Barros and others (n 62) 141.

¹⁹³ Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act) (Text with EEA relevance) (PE/17/2022/REV/1), OJ L 265/1 (DMA).

¹⁹⁴ Recital 37, 70. Article 13(4) and (6).

render broader interpretations of the term somewhat overstretched. Therefore, Sánchez Chamorro et al. criticise the amalgamation of definitions and terms used to describe 'dark patterns' and suggest shifting the discussion to a more precise term such as 'manipulative designs'.¹⁹⁵ This term differentiation helps shift the focus from specific patterns to broader concerns about entire systems, design strategies, and contextual manipulation. Retaining the original understanding of dark patterns as design tricks used on apps and websites at the UI level, while using other terms for systemic and functional, personalised designs, could prevent terminological dilution and confusion, ultimately supporting more effective regulation. However, achieving clarity is unlikely to be easy, given the continuously diversified interaction modalities (e.g., via voice assistants (VAs), virtual reality (VR)) between users and digital services, which extend beyond traditional graphical UIs to a systemic level in practice. Additionally, the broad interpretation of 'interface' as 'any software' in the DSA appears to anticipate such conceptual dilution.¹⁹⁶ Nevertheless, regardless of the uncertainty around terminology, which necessitates more future legal clarification, the term 'dark patterns' should, for now, be applauded and valued for its role in raising public awareness about the risks of unchecked and imbalanced design power wielded by digital choice architects.

Secondly, an expanding scope might also complicate regulatory decision-making concerning the ability to retrospectively classify some existing system-level designs as dark patterns, as these practices may have become normalised. For instance, HCI researchers might view targeted advertising or algorithmic/discriminative pricing as analogous to dark design patterns and express concerns that such designs could lead to excessive 'wealth surplus extraction' detrimental to consumer welfare. Yet, this type of harm is not prominently addressed in legal discussions.¹⁹⁷ Further research might explore other dark pattern types that reflect inherent discrepancies in value assessment between legal and HCI researchers.

¹⁹⁵ Lorena Sánchez Chamorro, Kerstin Bongard-Blanchy and Vincent Koenig, 'Ethical Tensions in UX Design Practice: Exploring the Fine Line Between Persuasion and Manipulation in Online Interfaces', *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference* (ACM 2023) 2418 <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3563657.3596013>>.

¹⁹⁶ Weiwei Yi, 'Gaming the Mind: Unmasking "Dark Patterns" in Video Games' [2024] *Internet Policy Review* <<https://policyreview.info/articles/news/unmasking-dark-patterns-video-games/1739>> accessed 2 July 2024.

¹⁹⁷ See eg Narayanan and others (n 38); Susser and Grimaldi (n 38). One possible explanation could be that practices such as differentiated pricing can be seen as pro-competition and fall into the scope which traders have the right to decide. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, *Personalised Pricing in the Digital Era* (DAF/COMP(2018)13, 20 November 2018). Therefore, the practice of algorithmic pricing and the extended extraction of wealth surplus per se is unlikely a 'legally regulatable' dark design pattern.

In summary, the ongoing expansion of the dark patterns scope could hinder the formulation of a practical and self-contained regulatory framework; yet, such uncertainty regarding the scope of dark patterns also signals how they have been symbolised and interpreted as an unattended and pressing need to rein unfair digital design and safeguard better digital environments for the general public. Given the interdisciplinary nature of 'dark patterns', the question of how the concept should be positioned in relation to other related concepts and how to address the peripheral boundary issue would be best determined collaboratively by HCI and legal researchers. The opportunities for further research are discussed in Section 6.4.¹⁹⁸

6.2. Promising technical and regulatory solutions

6.2.1. Compatible technical solutions and design accountability check frameworks

Despite the inherent conceptual problems of dark patterns that make current regulations appear less than ideal, we argue that our findings on scholars' proposed solutions (Section 5.3.2.3) highlight promising routes to more comprehensive future regulation as they are proactive and reflective of legal principles such as 'privacy by design and by default' and 'fairness'. These solutions should receive more attention from policymakers and be integrated into the regulatory framework. In the meantime, we also propose that different approaches need to be considered for different legal regimes.

Solutions such as direct technical design-embedded solutions (e.g., Personal Information Management Systems (PIMs), document engineering, browser-based approaches) may help achieve standardised and centralised decision-making environments and thus effectively eliminate the pain points of the existing decentralised, unstable and one-directional decision-making architectures that contribute to the potency of dark patterns. These measures may also salvage the individualism approach as well as the consent mechanism. However, they are usually raised predominantly in privacy-related contexts and focus more on data protection and privacy laws, which represent only one aspect of values that dark patterns undermine.

Comparatively, we see more potential in indirect accountability assessment frameworks for UX design (e.g., the 'feature parity check' for opt-out mechanisms, 'procedural accountability' assessment), as they introduce promising paradigmatic changes that align well with laws that protect personal data, privacy, consumer protection and online safety in general. This potential

¹⁹⁸ There have been voices from academics calling for and contributing to a unified ontology of dark patterns, which could enhance the regulability of dark patterns, especially for types that have been widely recognised and share many common characteristics. This could be a promising strategy to address the most salient dark patterns first before regulating the deeper forms. See Colin M. Gray, Cristiana Santos, and Nataliia Bielova, 'Towards a Preliminary Ontology of Dark Patterns Knowledge', *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM 2023).

for change is reflected in legal researchers' explicit calls for expanding the assessment scope of UX design beyond the consent moment to achieve 'fairness by design'.¹⁹⁹ This alignment suggests that a broader assessment framework for UX design to address dark patterns is gaining theoretical momentum.

We also find that, although both data protection and privacy law and consumer protection law aim to tackle similar problems related to individual decision-making which are susceptible to manipulative choice architectures, there is a notable disparity in the number of technical solutions addressing dark patterns in these two areas.²⁰⁰ For example, only Mathur et al. discuss using publicly outsourced flagging and machine-learning-based classifiers in browsers to curb dark patterns on shopping websites as a regulatory approach substantially more than in other papers on consumer welfare that we reviewed.²⁰¹ This disparity in the number of solutions suggests that the protective paradigm of consumer protection law might inherently be weaker than that of data protection and privacy. The 'privacy by design and by default' principle justifies stronger measures to guarantee the default status of privacy, endorsing more innovative technical solutions to regulate the choice architectures regarding personal data and privacy. Comparatively, consumer protection law relies on the understanding of (transactional) fairness between traders and consumers, where users/consumers are more likely to be left without protection, as the line deemed fair as well as the assessment scope is not uniform for individuals. Meanwhile, shown in our scholarly corpus, there is a scarcity of empirical legal studies on consumer protection frameworks based on consumer interpretations of different dark patterns. Consumers are left to rely on self-regulation and self-help remedies (as suggested by Mathur et al.), but these are likely blocked by the lack of a 'right to repair' that could override IP protections on software/interface design,²⁰² where the possibility of applying exemptions to IP protections outside a research context is low, thus disincentivising the development and maintenance of the anti-dark pattern tools benefiting the public. Ultimately, even for self-help remedies, people lack the tools and legal support to defend themselves against dark patterns and the inherently unilateral power of design.

6.2.2. Practical design guidelines across regimes

We argue that the primary criticism of the sufficiency of existing regulations centres on the difficulty of determining whether a design employs dark patterns, leading to widespread calls for

¹⁹⁹ Mark Leiser and Wen-Ting Yang (n 81); Wiener (n 96).

²⁰⁰ This discrepancy also speaks to the previous findings that consumer protection law is more criticised for the interpretation of provisions, while data protection and privacy law is more criticised for their enforcement quality.

²⁰¹ Mathur and others (n 41).

²⁰² Kollnig and others (n 85).

clear guidelines on assessment or design.²⁰³ For instance, it is proposed that industry-led ethical design guidelines of a self-regulation nature could serve as a baseline in courts to determine whether 'professional diligence' is fulfilled, according to which a design can be judged as 'unfair' ('dark') or not under the UCPD.²⁰⁴ However, while we believe industrial-led design guidelines could ensure the practicality of the guidelines as the companies and designers are better involved, considering our finding that the inherent conflicts of interest is one of the root problems of dark patterns and given the existing limitations of current soft law, stronger meta-regulation may be necessary. For critical aspects of design that are likely to cause significant distortions in user behaviour, certain mandatory standardisation could be implemented. Furthermore, considering the diverse sectoral contexts in which dark patterns propagate and the varied service-offering logic of businesses, design guidelines should be sector-specific (e.g., Gamification might be more justifiable for education-oriented services, while it should be less permissible for public-facing investment and finance services or gig economy platforms) and also technique-tailored (e.g., the interaction modalities of conversational UI, Mixed Reality, video games would require more detailed specifications, as most well-recognised dark patterns are Graphical UI-based) with specific use cases for better clarification.²⁰⁵ In the meantime, general design guidelines could be provided (e.g., under the DSA or the future Digital Fairness Act (DFA)) to act as general design rules for whichever sectors that show less need for tailored guidelines.

It is worth stressing that the line between appropriate and dark design is not fixed and permanent. According to Bernstein's theory on the window of reshaping technology, the status of no regulation continually changes the norm in the commercial environment day by day, where consumers might become more tolerant of easy-to-perceive and widely used dark patterns, making them the new normal.²⁰⁶ However, this assumption applies only to "average" consumers; for "vulnerable" consumers who are less adaptive to the change of norm, the basic types could still be exploitative. This also explains why, especially in the context of consumer protection law, taking the initiative to form rules and 'cut the line' might be more practical and contributive than 'finding the line'. The more hesitant policymakers are, the more likely the overall line will gradually shift to a side where more consumer welfare is compromised (especially in the form of

²⁰³ As the regulations on dark patterns seem to scatter in many different laws (as our findings show), the question of how to reconcile these laws and arrange the hierarchy of legal forces, ex-ante or ex-post is outside the scope of our research.

²⁰⁴ Silvia De Conca (n 54). and UCPD Guidance 2021, 101.

²⁰⁵ For example, it is found that there are more unique dark pattern types identified in an XR environment that cannot be attributed to the current mainstream taxonomies of dark patterns. See Veronika Krauß and others, 'What Makes XR Dark? Examining Emerging Dark Patterns in Augmented and Virtual Reality through Expert Co-Design' (2024) 31 ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction 1.

²⁰⁶ Bernstein (n 1).

unmeasurable harm), especially considering the already imbalanced relationship between consumers and companies that deploy dark patterns.

6.3. Diligent designs as a new paradigm: beyond harm-proving and embrace a proactive technical design-embedded regulatory framework

Our findings show that the harms caused by dark patterns vary in nature, enabling different laws to intervene to address these harms and protect the corresponding legal interests and fundamental rights. However, as our discussion demonstrates, it remains difficult to prove the existence, types, and magnitude of harms, which may further hamper effective regulation of dark patterns.²⁰⁷ Consequently, the regulation of dark patterns could benefit from a paradigm that is less anchored on harms, but more on other concepts, such as (due) diligence.

Due diligence is at the heart of the United Nation's Framework for Business and Human Rights.²⁰⁸ 'This concept describes the steps a company must take to become aware of, prevent and address adverse human rights impacts'²⁰⁹ and it stresses a general (social) responsibility for business enterprises to respect human rights. As dark patterns undermine individual autonomy, which is considered part of the fundamental human right to dignity,²¹⁰ due diligence could serve as a stronger legal basis to justify a more proactive, ex-ante regulatory approach to dark patterns.

The idea of due diligence and diligent designs is already present in the current legal framework, but it is still worth further development and clarification by legal researchers. For example, the due diligence confined to professionals as professional diligence in the UCPD traditionally sets a premise of transactional decisions or potential commercial trading relationships.²¹¹ One key point is that, once dark patterns become the new normal, or given the current freemium and attention-seeking business model where revenue and contracts come from a third party, the

²⁰⁷ Our findings and discussions are corroborated by the comprehensive review on the taxonomy of dark pattern harms and discussions on how these harms might face challenges in the current designs of material and especially non-material harm redress in the EU and national liability regimes. See Cristiana Santos, Viktorija Morozovaite and Silvia De Conca, 'No Harm No Foul: How Harms Caused by Dark Patterns Are Conceptualised and Tackled under EU Data Protection, Consumer and Competition Laws' [2025] Information & Communications Technology Law 1.

²⁰⁸ John Gerard Ruggie and UN Special Representative of the Secretary-General on Human Rights and Transnational Corporations and Other Business Enterprises, 'Protect, Respect and Remedy: A Framework for Business and Human Rights : Report of the Special Representative of the Secretary-General on the Issue of Human Rights and Transnational Corporations and Other Business Enterprises, John Ruggie' <<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/625292>> accessed 7 March 2025.

²⁰⁹ *ibid* 17.

²¹⁰ European Commission, 'Commission Guidelines on prohibited artificial intelligence practices established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AI Act)' Brussels, 4.2.2025 C(2025) 884 final, 18

²¹¹ Chris Willett, 'Fairness and Consumer Decision Making under the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive' (2010) 33 Journal of Consumer Policy 247, 249.

traditional understanding of commercial relationships on which the UCPD is built would need to be updated to comprehensively cover non-transactional moments and be incorporated explicitly into future consumer protection legislation. Another key point is that the due diligence concept in professional contexts relies on industrial consensus over the standards of 'professional diligence'. As our findings elaborate, the freemium and attention-seeking business model could hinder the development of standards, leading to failed self-regulation in some industries. Therefore, even within the context of consumer protection, the future DFA might need to impose stricter requirements for establishing professional diligence standards, as discussed in the previous section.

Comparatively, we see a more progressive paradigm shift embodied in technical design-embedded solutions in the Digital Services Act (DSA), alongside the corresponding internalisation of the due diligence concept that extends beyond contextualised professional diligence.

The concept of due diligence underlies the obligations for intermediary services as outlined in the DSA.²¹² Although the DSA comprises mixed regulatory objectives and only regulates dark patterns on online platforms, the technical design-embedded initiatives of the DSA are significant models for future legislation that aims for *ex-ante* better digital designs. For example, the regulatory online infrastructural database for transparency reporting on content moderation,²¹³ and the repository for advertisement transparency,²¹⁴ can be the forerunners for future infrastructural archiving for Terms of Conditions/Services, End-User License Agreements (EULA), Privacy Policies, where text-based dark patterns generally exist, for version control for public and academic supervision. Moreover, the mandatory technical designs (e.g., to enable recipients' control over content recommendation (to a certain level),²¹⁵ to attach prominent markings of advertising information on the user interface,²¹⁶ to ban targeted advertising to minors)²¹⁷ may pioneer more technical design-embedded solutions as obligated diligent design.

Future digital regulations (such as the proposed Digital Fairness Act) could require different versions of software designs for different user groups. This approach is similar to the existing user-centric transparency idea elaborated in Guidelines on transparency by the 29 Working

²¹² See eg Recital 40 and 41, Chapter III, DSA.

²¹³ Article 24 (5), DSA

²¹⁴ Article 39, DSA

²¹⁵ Article 27, DSA

²¹⁶ Article 26, DSA

²¹⁷ Article 28 (2), DSA.

Party, but goes beyond the context of data protection. This means that the regulations may request traders to implement (professionally) diligent designs to prevent the exploitation of digital vulnerabilities. Children, old people, and other vulnerable consumers who are more susceptible to dark patterns and other harmful designs deserve, by default, software versions with the 'best' and consistent design practices, where dark patterns are eliminated by more intuitive, cleaner and more standardised UX designs. On the other hand, for the public who could have individual vulnerabilities which can potentially be exploited, they may access this version through a simplified self-claiming/reporting of individual vulnerabilities. This is because, while it is difficult to prove and redress non-material harms of dark patterns, it would also be inappropriate for companies with design power to assume that individuals have no vulnerabilities and would not suffer from derivative harms due to careless or reckless designs.²¹⁸ More importantly, this operation would not cannibalise the social resources for the well-recognised vulnerable groups, considering the flexibility and scalability of digital design resources by nature. Under the name of diligent design, researchers may acquire a better position to explore and experiment with practical measures that help mitigate the designs that elude regulation due to the dilemmatic 'average/vulnerable consumer' dichotomy. Regarding possible pathways to practical diligent design models, some scholars have proposed a promising assessment framework for evaluating the risks of dark pattern harms, identifying factors that influence the vulnerabilities of different groups.²¹⁹ This framework could serve as a useful roadmap for developing sector-specific guidance to assess services, including different versions of the same service designed for distinct vulnerable groups. We would like to encourage legal researchers to become more involved in the formulation of these promising theoretical foundations against dark patterns and other harmful designs.

In conclusion, such a potential shift to diligent design, whether based on professions in e-commerce or other sectors, can be understood as a pathway to a broader concept of 'fairness', which is a social value pursued by different regulatory regimes. It may help dismiss the requirement of evidential harms that barricades more proactive regulation and may also mitigate the line-cutting issue attached to a narrow interpretation of 'fairness' in digital designs, especially when the wording may easily be read as a rigid balancing between different stakeholders (e.g., consumers and traders, users and whoever holds the design power of the

²¹⁸ This approach can be seen as in line with Willis' approach that suggests reversing the burden of proof, but we propose to make it happen at the stage of users' actual interaction with the digital interface rather than a later judicial moment. See n 157.

²¹⁹ Arianna Rossi and others, 'Who Is Vulnerable to Deceptive Design Patterns? A Transdisciplinary Perspective on the Multi-Dimensional Nature of Digital Vulnerability' (2024) 55 *Computer Law & Security Review* 106031.

digital choice architecture) out of context. Such rooting of diligent design on (social/professional) responsibility could not only justify eliminating dark patterns but also support further calls for pro-user diversification of UX designs.

Moreover, effective regulation necessitates embracing multistakeholderism to develop more comprehensive regulatory approaches against the backdrop of uncertainties surrounding dark patterns,²²⁰ calling for a fundamental paradigm shift in mindset among regulators, designers, and other stakeholders. Even without considering the expansion of the connotation of dark patterns and the inherent uncertainty of the term dark patterns, the findings presented in this paper clearly demonstrate that the harm caused by dark patterns impacts various legal interests and values addressed by different regulatory mechanisms, such as financial law, consumer protection, and data privacy. Consequently, it is essential to integrate flexible, technically-informed approaches rather than confining regulatory responses strictly within the boundaries of specific legal frameworks. Embedding this pluralistic perspective from the outset of regulatory intervention and at the design stage of the initial application of new technologies can facilitate comprehensive and proactive measures against manipulative practices. As outlined in section 6.2.2, industry-level guidance that promotes such a shift in perspective is vital. This approach emphasises a conceptual change rather than the rigid pursuit of conformity across different laws. Concurrently, the importance of multistakeholderism should be stressed, highlighting collaboration among legislators, technologists, industry leaders, and civil society to foster adaptable and effective regulation.²²¹ Tools developed by HCI researchers, such as taxonomies and automated detection methods, can support both enforcement and system design, achieving fairness by design.

Effective dialogue between regulators is paramount in formulating cohesive regulatory and industrial policies, ensuring consistency in legal terminology and enforcement when overlaps occur. Initiatives such as the Digital Clearinghouse 2.0 proposed recently by the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), which serves as an enhanced forum uniting authorities responsible for various components of the EU Digital Regulation package, are particularly noteworthy in this context.²²² Similarly, the UK's Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF), which unites four UK regulatory bodies, serves as an important initiative aimed at creating

²²⁰ Mark Raymond and Laura DeNardis, 'Multistakeholderism: Anatomy of an Inchoate Global Institution' (2015) 7 *International Theory* 572.

²²¹ *ibid.*

²²² EDPS, 'Digital Clearinghouse 2.0' (2025) <https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/digital-clearinghouse-20_en> accessed 30 March 2025.

coherence and resolving potential tensions between regulatory regimes through collaborative engagement on complex regulatory challenges.²²³

6.4. Future research

The shift to a more proactive regulatory framework supporting diligent design against dark patterns would not come into being without collaborative transdisciplinary research. The proposal would face strong resistance, as it may force business entities with design power to change their models, burden SMEs, or cause excessive interference with fundamental rights (e.g., the freedom to conduct a business under the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights or the freedom of commercial speech under the US First Amendment). Therefore, HCI researchers may continue leading practical design schemes, serving as preliminary substitutes, supported by robust user research, experiments, and feasibility studies. With grounded evidence and implementable solutions, the asymmetry of bargaining power, information, and design can be better mitigated.

This effort needs support from legal researchers and policymakers. Legal researchers and policymakers should join early in design development. Legal researchers can enrich diligent designs from human rights protection, mitigating the possible hindrances from other laws, such as intellectual property law, during the process. We further call for a shift in policymaking that better acknowledges pro-user, individual, and public technical design-embedded solutions as a form of regulation. While these solutions may not necessarily be difficult or costly to implement, companies and traders lack the incentive to adopt them—especially when doing so conflicts with their business model and financial interests.

Another research direction corresponds to the ‘scope’ problem discussed in Section 6.1.3. Recent cross-disciplinary work on uniform taxonomies and ontologies of dark patterns provides a strong source of design guidance.²²⁴ While the ontology is self-contained and comprehensive, we encourage both HCI and legal researchers to review and calibrate the peripheral boundary of the ontology. For example, there is a need to determine how the current ontology should be positioned in relation to other important concepts that, as argued by scholars in our findings, intersect with it, such as personalisation and artificial intelligence. For example, further development of personalisation as a type of (meso-level) dark pattern would benefit

²²³ DRCF, ‘The Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF) Brings Together Four UK Regulators to Deliver a Coherent Approach to Digital Regulation for the Benefit of People and Businesses Online.’ (www.drcf.org.uk, 15 September 2023) <<https://www.drcf.org.uk/>> accessed 30 March 2025.

²²⁴ Gray and others, ‘An Ontology of Dark Patterns Knowledge’ (n 8).

substantially from more low-level examples.²²⁵ For AI not typically used for personalisation, the question could involve dark patterns' relationship with subliminal, manipulative, and deceptive AI practices, as dark patterns have been positioned as an important source of knowledge to understand the prohibited AI practices under Article 5(1)(a).²²⁶

7. Limitations

Despite the review choosing the most pertinent keywords of dark patterns and disciplines for database searching, some pertinent papers might not be enlisted due to the different use of terms or indexing of disciplines. Additionally, as we only focus on English-written scholarship, this article might not reflect dark patterns of research written in another different linguistic background. Meanwhile, the difficulty in tagging some papers, especially those HCI researcher-led papers to which law researchers substantially contributed, as either law or HCI due to the ongoing deepening collaboration in dark pattern research from an interdisciplinary perspective, and consequently, our strategic inclusion of these papers as law papers to enrich our analysis may, from another perspective, leading to less heterogeneous findings for RQ2. On the other hand, papers which are difficult to distribute are not substantial in number so our findings are not substantially influenced. We did not systematically identify the actors (e.g., platforms, designers, legislators and enforcers) involved in the regulation of dark patterns and the proposed responsibilities upon them, which may be suitable for future research on a more micro and practical level. We primarily adopted an EU perspective in the discussion section to engage with the findings, which may make our insights less relevant in other jurisdictions.

8. Conclusion

Drawing on an interdisciplinary review of legal and HCI scholarship, this paper has shown how dark patterns are framed, how harms are understood, and how regulation has been approached. We found that legal debates draw heavily on HCI definitions while gradually expanding the concept of dark patterns to capture systemic issues embedded in the digital environment. This broadening highlights that dark patterns are not simply digital versions of offline unfair practices but part of a deeper structural challenge.

Our analysis revealed layered harms at the individual, market, and societal levels, alongside the involvement of diverse legal frameworks beyond data protection, consumer, and competition

²²⁵ See eg Krauß and others (n 208); Mark Leiser and Cristiana Santos, 'Dark Patterns, Enforcement, and the Emerging Digital Design Acquis: Manipulation beneath the Interface' (2024) 15 *European Journal of Law and Technology* <<https://ejlt.org/index.php/ejlt/article/view/990>> accessed 23 September 2024; European Commission (n 19) 18–19; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (n 17) 28–29.

²²⁶ European Commission (n 210) 47–48.

law. Yet across these regimes, common problems of theory, interpretation, and enforcement hinder comprehensive regulation.

We synthesised three directions of regulatory response: paradigmatic changes in legal doctrines, refinements to existing frameworks with stronger enforcement and collaboration, and technical design-embedded solutions such as automated detection and accountability checks. Taken together, these proposals show both the creativity of current scholarship and the persistent barriers posed by the elusive nature, uncertain harms, and expanding scope of dark patterns.

Ultimately, we argue for a shift toward more proactive and preventive regulation centred on concepts like fairness and diligent design. Such an approach requires closer collaboration between legal and HCI researchers and the development of practical design guidelines and accountability mechanisms to build a sustainable and resilient framework against manipulative digital practices.

9. Appendix

The codebook for content analysis

Research Questions	Sub-research questions	For HCI paper	For Law paper
RQ1: What are the basic characteristics of the scholarship on the regulation of dark patterns? (Section 5.1)	What are the 'Framings' of the studies? (Section 5.1.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluative: Leveraging existing taxonomies to identify whether something is an example of a dark pattern. • Descriptive: Using examples to illustrate power, impact, or attributes. • Detection-focused: Creating and deploying an automated detection technique. • Taxonomy-building: Defining new types of dark patterns or consolidating existing patterns. • Problematising: Identifying limitations of taxonomies and identifying gaps in current literature. • Experimental/Causal: identifying generalisable causal mechanisms. • Non-empirical/Theoretical: Contain no empirical elements or are argumentative. • <i>(Note: codes are originally from Gray et al.'s codebook except for 'Non-empirical/Theoretical')</i> 	N/A
	What are the 'Aims' of the studies? (Section 5.1.1)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptualisation of concepts: (Re)conceptualising, re- or de-construction of a concept that is either dark patterns per se or is related to it. • Assessing the existing law: Assessing the current legal framework regarding its capacity to regulate a (new) phenomenon. The conclusion could be negative, positive or mixed. • Assessing the legitimacy of practice: It could be practices or an overall phenomenon that embraces or is a component of dark patterns.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposing problem-solving schemes: The solutions could be technical, legal, or paradigmatic.
	What are the 'Contexts' of the literature? (Section 5.1.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platform effects: When the paper particularly discusses the roles and effects of platforms or similar subjects in dark pattern-related practices. Digital Services: When the context is general and does not fall into other codes, or when a macro perspective is taken in general. Games and gaming: When the paper mainly focuses on players, game designs and designers. Website and apps: When the focus is particularly detailed on user interaction with UI/software at a micro-level (e.g., consent banners, the checkout process on websites). Artificial Intelligence: When AI is a major focus of discussion in the paper. 	
	What are the 'Jurisdictions' involved in the studies? (Section 5.1.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> United States European Union (including member states) Multi-Jurisdiction United Kingdom Canada China 	
RQ2: How does legal scholarship engage with and interpret the concept of dark patterns? (Section 5.2)	What roles do the dark pattern discussions play in the law literature? (Section 5.2.1)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As an example: The discussion on dark patterns is limited, usually appearing as scattered sentences or paragraphs. As a case/theme: Dark patterns are analysed relatively independently, as one of the cases or themes in the paper. As the main focus: Dark patterns are the main focus of the study. As the context/backdrop: Dark patterns are depicted as the background phenomenon that ushers in the discussion of other focuses.
	How does the law literature refer to definitions and approach taxonomies of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.2)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not engaging with taxonomies: The paper does not engage with dark pattern taxonomies at all and only uses the concept of dark patterns. As an example of the dark pattern phenomenon: Some types of dark patterns or meso-level categories are mentioned to support an argument.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As the objective of the analysis: There is a substantial analysis based on existing taxonomies. <i>(Note: For findings on the most-cited studies referencing dark pattern definitions in legal scholarship, see Section 5.2.2.1.)</i>
RQ3: What laws, doctrinal challenges, and pathways for reform are discussed to regulate dark patterns? (Section 5.3)	What laws regarding dark patterns are discussed? (Section 5.3.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data protection and privacy law: (Papers that discuss) sectoral laws aimed at protecting data privacy or data protection. Consumer protection law: (Papers that discuss) sectoral laws aimed at safeguarding consumer rights and fair trade with consumers. Competition law: (Papers that discuss) sectoral laws aimed at promoting fair competition in the market, preventing anti-competitive practices and the abuse of market power. Contract law: (Papers that discuss) sectoral laws that govern the formation, execution, and enforcement of agreements between parties. The laws in the EU digital strategy package: (Papers that discuss) EU legislation under the Digital Agenda for Europe (See https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/64/digital-agenda-for-europe). Law of fundamental rights: (Papers that discuss) the highest legal sources that form the constitutional foundation of a jurisdiction (e.g., the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, the U.S. First Amendment). Theories of law: (Papers that discuss) legal theories or normative concepts broadly relevant across different legal sectors or frameworks. Other laws: (Papers that discuss) laws not covered under the categories above. 	

Research Questions	Sub-research questions	Themes
RQ2: How does legal scholarship engage with and interpret the concept of dark patterns? (Section 5.2)	What are the root problems of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The invisibility of digital design • Platform effects and market competition • Human bias and vulnerability • (Attention-seeking) business models and conflicts of interest • Derivative problems: Power asymmetry over information and design
	What are the identified harms of dark patterns? (Section 5.2.4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harms to individuals • Harms to the market and competition • Harms to society
RQ3: What laws, doctrinal challenges, and pathways for reform are discussed to regulate dark patterns? (Section 5.3)	What are the doctrinal challenges of the corresponding laws? (Section 5.3.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The fuzzy boundaries between concepts (Theories of law) • The problem of the types and levels of 'harm' (Theories of law) • The problematic dichotomy of average and vulnerable consumers (Consumer protection law) • The problem of the consent mechanism & individual approach to data regulation (Data protection and privacy law) • The outdated theory of competition law, misposition of platform power (Competition Law) • The new shadow cast by AI (DSA and AIA) • Fundamental rights: The right to autonomy and commercial speech • The contradiction in contracts (Contract law) • Limitations of the current soft law and self-regulation
	What revisions of regulation are proposed to solve dark patterns? (Section 5.3.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposal 1: Paradigmatic changes of legal doctrines • Proposal 2: Refining the existing regulatory frameworks • Proposal 3: Technical design-embedded solution and design accountability check

CREATE

Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy

School of Law / University of Glasgow

10 The Square

Glasgow G12 8QQ

www.create.ac.uk

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